

The Dipterans (Insecta: Diptera) of the Rila Mountains

Zdravko HUBENOV

Abstract: A total of 1003 two-winged species that belong to 58 families have been reported from the Rila Mts. The Tachinidae (162 species or 16.1%) and Syrphidae (149 species or 14.8%) are the most numerous. The great number of species (736 species – 73.4%) has been found in the beech forest belt. The established species belong to 84 areographical categories. The dipterous fauna can be divided into two main groups: 1) species with Mediterranean type of distribution (48 species or 4.8%); more thermophilic and distributed mainly in the southern parts of the Palaearctic. Three species of southern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well; 2) species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (955 species or 95.2%); more cold-resistant and widely distributed in the Palaearctic. Two hundred fifty-five species of northern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well. The Holomediterranean (eight species or 0.8%) and South European (seven species or 0.7%) forms are best represented in the first group. The European (183 species or 18.2%), Holarctic (124 species or 12.4%), Holoeurosiberian (82 species or 8.2%) and Transpalaearctic (78 species or 7.8%) taxa prevail in the second group. The endemic species are 12 (1.2%). The zoogeographical character of the fauna is determined by the second group. The distribution of the separate categories in the vegetation belts of the Rila Mts. is presented.

Key words: Diptera, Bulgaria, Rila Mts., faunistic composition, areographical characteristics

Introduction

The first data on Diptera of the Rila Mts. were reported by JOAKIMOFF (1899) and NEDELKOV (1909, 1910, 1912). Between the two world wars ENDERLEIN (1924, 1926), CZERNÝ (1930), KOMAREK & VIMMER (1934), SZILÁDY (1934), ZILAHÍ (1934), DRENSKI (1934, 1939a, 1939b, 1943), DRENSKI (1936, 1939), JACENTKOVSKY (1936, 1937, 1939), LACKSCHEWITZ (1940a, 1940b), BUHR (1941) and ARNDT (1943) published data on the two-winged fauna from the mountain. After the World War II, the first work which included materials from the Rila Mts., was published by NIKOLOVA (1950). Then significant number of articles related to dipterans of the Rila Mts., including applied entomological works as well, (BURESCH & LAZAROV, 1956; DRENSKI, 1957a, 1957b, 1958; MARINOV, 1957; BOŽKOV, 1959, 1991; GRIGOROV, 1962; NAIDENOV, 1962; LAVČIEV, 1964a, 1964b, 1966, 1967, 1980, 2003; ROZKOŠNY, 1965; LECLERCQ, 1966; BANKOWSKA, 1967a, 1967b; HRADSKY & MOUCHA, 1967; OLSUFJEV et al., 1967; BERON, 1972; CHVALA et al., 1972; STARÝ, 1973, 1974a, 1974b, 1976; JELJASOVA, 1975; BESHOVSKI, 1978, 1982, 1984, 1985, 1995, 2004a, 2004b, 2007, 2008, 2009, 2013; BEIGER, 1979; HUBENOV, 1980, 1983; TRENČEV, 1980a, 1980b, 1980c, 1980d; BARTÁK, 1981; LEHR, 1981; JOOST, 1982; LAUTERER, 1983; KRZEMIŃSKI, 1984; LAVČIEV et al., 1984; VÄISÄNEN, 1984; MENDL, 1986; KRZEMIŃSKI & STARÝ, 1989; MICHAILOVA, 1989; POVOLNÝ & VERVES, 1990; BECHEV, 1991, 1994, 1996, 2001, 2004, 2006, 2010; BESCHOVSKI & MINKOVA, 1991; SKUHRAVA et al., 1991; BESCHOVSKI, LANGOUROV, 1997; MARKOVA, 1997, 2006; GANEVA, 1998, 1999, 2000; BESHOVSKI & ZATWARNICKI, 2000, 2001a, 2001b, 2002, 2004; DZHAMBASOV, 2000; KEČEV, 2005, 2006, 2007, 2010; PAPP, 2010). The hydrobiological (VALKANOV, 1941; DIMITROV, 1962, 1963, 1966; RUSSEV, 1966; KOVACHEV, 1973, 1976, 2000; STOICHEV, 1996, 2000a, 2000b, 2002, 2004; STOICHEV, CHERNEV, 2001; STOICHEV, DANOVA, 2003) and biospeleological studies (BERON, 1994, 2006, 2015) have a faunistic contribution.

The data are fragmentary, concern separated parts of the mountain and are scattered in different

articles which are not specially referred to the Rila Mts. There are more systematic studies of the explored territory for the families Limoniidae, Cecidomyiidae, Simuliidae, Chironomidae, Syrphidae, Agromyzidae, Chloropidae, Muscidae and Tachinidae. Generalised studies on the Diptera fauna of the Rila Mts. are lacking. In the management plan of the Rila National Park, the dipterans (386 species) are scrutinized according to parts of the mountains, without exact localities (HUBENOV et al., 2000) and without including all families. In the ecological assessment of the Rila Monastery Nature Park (PEEV, 2003), the dipterans are not included.

The aim of this paper is to collate the data concerning the study level, fauna and zoogeography of the two-winged insects of the Rila Mts., Rila National Park and Rila Monastery Nature Park.

Study Area, Materials and Methods

RILA MTS. are situated in the South-West Bulgaria. To the north Dzhubrena River, Klisurska Col (1025 m a.s.l.) and Klisurchitsa River separate it from the Verila Mts. The Samokovsko Field (950 m a.s.l.), Bistritsa River, Borovetska Col (1305 m a.s.l.), the Malka Slivnitsa, Slivnitsa and Maritsa Rivers (until Dolnya Banya Town – 640 m a.s.l.) separate it from the Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts. The Kostenets-Dolna Banya Basin (520-680 m a.s.l.) and Maritsa River, until the confluence of Yadenitsa River, separate the Rila Mts. from the most southeastern parts of the Ihtimanska Sredna Gora Mts. To the east the border runs along the Yadenitsa River, Yundola Col (1375 m a.s.l.), Yundola Village (1400 m a.s.l.), Lyuta Reka River, Avramova Col (1295 m a.s.l.), Dreshnets River and Mesta River until Razlog Basin (940 m a.s.l.) which separates the Rila Mts. from the Rhodope Mts. To the south the mountain reaches the Razlog Basin and is separated from the Pirin Mts. through the Rablevska Reka River, Predel Col (1140 m a.s.l.) and the Kulina, Elovitsa and Gradevska Rivers. To the west the mountain borders on the valley of the Struma River from the confluence of the Gradevska River (Simitli Basin – 360 m a.s.l.), through the Blagoevgrad Basin (360 m a.s.l.) until the confluence of the Dzherman River and the Dzherman Valley from its confluence into the Struma River until Dupnitsa Plain (400-700 m a.s.l.).

The Rila Mts. are a part of the Rila-Rhodope massif and belongs to the Rila-Pirin mountain group. The mountain stretches west-east and is over 70 km long and 50 km wide. The maximum height at Musala Peak is 2925 m a.s.l.. The total area of the mountain

is 2629 km² (2.37% of the Bulgarian territory), with the average height of 1487 m and 18 peaks over 2700 m a.s.l. and more than 100 peaks above 2000 m a.s.l. It is divided into four parts: **NORTHWEST** (Lakatishka Rila, ridges Otovitsa-Kabul, Polich-Kalin and Malyovitsa-Mechit), **CENTRAL** (ridges Skakavitsa and Rilets), **EAST** (ridges Musala and Ibar) and **SOUTHWEST** (ridges Arizmanitsa and Ravnik). The Rila Mts. represent a silicate massif consisting essentially of granites. In the Pleistocene glacial forms (carlings, cirques, trog valleys and moraines) have been formed. Gravity forms of alpine type (scree, stone rivers and seas, snowslide cones, gullies and moraine shafts) are characteristic of its high parts. The Rila Mts. are under the influence of the Intermediate-Continental and Continental-Mediterranean climatic regions and include parts of the Rila-Osogovo and Mountain climatic regions (STANEV, 1991). The Rila Mts. are a main hydrographic node, from which originate the Iskar, Maritsa and Mesta Rivers. In the cirques of the Rila Mts., 190 glacial lakes are situated. Most lakes are situated between 2300 and 2400 m a.s.l. The Ledenoto Ezero Lake below the Musala Peak is the highest (2709 m a.s.l.). The Rila Mts. belong to the same titled region of the Illyrian Province of the European deciduous forest area. The vegetation is differentiated in a system of six vegetation zones (STOJANOV, 1966; VELCHEV et al., 1982, 1989; VELCHEV, TONKOV, 1986; BONDEV, 1991, 1997, 2002; VELCHEV, 1997, 2002): 1) Xerothermic oak forests, best presented in the northeast, west and south-west hillsides up to 500-700 m a.s.l.; 2) Mesophytic and xeromesophytic mixed forests, well presented in the west, east and south-east hillsides – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m a.s.l.; 3) Beech forests, best presented in the north, northeast and west parts of the mountain – from 900-1000 m to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.; 4) Coniferous forests, best presented in the north, east and south hillsides – from 1500-1600 m to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.; 5) Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 to 2500 m a.s.l.; 6) Alpine vegetation – above 2400-2500 m a.s.l. Under the human impact the vegetation has undergone destructive changes, expressed most strongly in the first two zones. Native vegetation in many places is destroyed and replaced by cultivated and derivative wood, shrubby and grass communities. The boundaries between the vegetation belts are not defined clearly and depending on the exposure, topography and human activities there are mixed zones up to 200-300 m a.s.l. The Rila Mts. belong to the Rila-Rhodope Zoogeographical Region and have an Eurosiberian faunistic character (GEORGIEV, 1982, 2002). The mountains are the richest in endemics

(268) and relicts (230) area in Bulgaria (HUBENOV, 2008).

The territory of the Rila National Park includes 81046 ha with the reserves Parangalitsa (1509 ha), Central Rila Reserve (12393.7 ha), Ibar (2248.6 ha) and Skakavitsa (70.8 ha). The park's boundary rarely descends below 1000 m a.s.l. (in the northeast and west parts) and usually lies considerably higher (above 1500-2000 m a.s.l.). The Rila Monastery Nature Park (27270 ha) with the Rila Monastery Forest Reserve (3678 ha) is also included in the mountains' territory. The protected areas cover over 40% of the total area of the mountain.

The material from the Rila Mts. has been collected after 1890 and the main part of it is stored in the National Museum of Natural History and the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research. A number of foreign entomologists have collected and published materials from Bulgaria, containing data about the Rila Mts. The material is collected from 160 localities (Table 1), combined in several starting points: south of Sapareva Banya Town, Panichishte holiday resort, Govedartsi Village, Samokov Town, Beli Iskar Village, Borovets Resort and Kostenets Village; south-east of Dupnitsa Town; east of the Rila Town, Pastra Village and Blagoevgrad Town; surroundings of the Rila Monastery; west of Yundola Area; north-west of Yakoruda Town; surroundings of the chalets Lovna, Vada, Skakavitsa, Rilski Ezera, Sedemte Ezera, Malyovitsa, Yastrebets, Musala, Zavrachitsa, Granchar, Ribni Ezera, Belmeken, Treshtenik, Makedoniya and Semkovo Holiday Resort. Some collectors did not give accurate localities on the labels and indicated only the Rila Mts. (for 111 species). For a number of widespread and numerous species the authors did not give the localities and mentioned they occur everywhere. Such species are included in the review only if they are reported from the Rila Mts.

Zoogeographical analysis for the species categorisation was used. This method allows obtaining data information about species complexes with different zoogeographical character based on the published data regarding species distribution and results of the faunistic research. The classification of the areas is based on the works of DE LATTIN (1967), MALICKY et al. (1983), GORODKOV (1984) and VIGNA TAGLIANTI et al. (1999). The inversion of the traditional nomenclature and the border between the West and East Palaearctic along the Ural Mts. of VIGNA TAGLIANTI et al. (1999) is not accepted (the border runs along the Yenisey River). To compare the fauna, CZEKANOWSKI-DICE-SÖRENSEN coefficient of similarity was used.

Abbreviations used: Figures – numbers of the localities in Table 1 and numbers in the References, **Roman numbers** – months of flight activity or period of collecting, ● – Rila National Park, ◆ – Rila Monastery Nature Park, ? – uncertain data or lack of data, +++ – species, reported for the first time and localities, from which species are reported for the first time, **atm** – Afrotropical-Mediterranean, **ba** – Boreoalpine, **ban** – Balkan-Anatolian, **bm** – Boreomontane, **cee** – Central and East European, **cse** – Central and South European, **csean** – Central and South European-Anatolian, **csee** – Central and South-East European, **cseean** – Central and South-East European-Anatolian, **cseeit** – Central and South-East European-Iran-Turanian, **cseel** – Central and South-East European-Lebanonian, **cseit** – Central and South European-Iran-Turanian, **csena** – Central and South European-North African, **des** – Disjunct Eurosiberian, **dp** – Disjunct Palaearctic, **dpo** – Disjunct Palaearctic-Oriental, **e** – European, **ean** – European-Anatolian, **eanna** – European-Anatolian-North African, **Eb** – Balkan endemic, **Ebg** – Bulgarian endemic, **Ebs** – Balkan subendemic, **eca** – European-Central Asian, **eeca** – East European-Central Asian, **eit** – European-Iran-Turanian, **em** – East Mediterranean, **ena** – European-North African, **Er** – Regional endemic, **esanca** – Eurosiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian, **esca** – Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **ess** – European and South Siberian, **eswa** – European-South-West Asian, **et** – European-Turanian, **ewca** – European-West Central Asian, **h** – Holarctic, **h*** – species introduced in North America, **ha** – Holarctic-Australian, **hat** – Holarctic-Afrotropical, **hata** – Holarctic-Afrotropical-Australian, **hn** – Holarctic-Neotropical, **hnat** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical, **hno** – Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental, **ho** – Holarctic-Oriental, **hoa** – Holarctic-Oriental-Australian, **hoes** – Holoeurosiberian, **hom** – Holomediterranean, **hop** – Holopalaearctic, **hpt** – Holarctic-Paleotropical, **hpta** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian, **hptn** – Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical, **I** – introduced species (immigrants), **k** – Cosmopolitan, **m** – montane, **mca** – Mediterranean-Central Asian, **mss** – Mediterranean and South Siberian, **msws** – Mediterranean and South-West Siberian, **mt** – Mediterranean-Turanian, **mwca** – Mediterranean-West Central Asian, **nemit** – Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian, **nm** – North Mediterranean, **nmca** – North Mediterranean-Central Asian, **nmt** – North Mediterranean-Turanian, **om** – Oriental-Mediterranean, **pa** – Palaearctic-Australian, **pat** – Palaearctic-Afrotropical, **pata** – Palaearctic-Afrotropical-Australian, **po** –

Table 1. Localities of Diptera from the Rila Mts.

Localities	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	GPS Navigation (°N, °E)	UTM Kode	Number of species
1. Bahchalaka (near Bistritsa Village)	1200	42°03'12.20"; 23°13'56.40"	FM85	1
2. Bela Mesta River	960-1650		GM16, GM25, GM26	19
3. Beli Iskar River	1070-1850		GM08, GM17	23
4. Beli Iskar Village (above the village)	1140	42°15'59.71"; 23°32'26.42"	GM08	1
5. Beli Iskar River, near Kovach Peak	2300-2500	42°06'51.16"; 23°34'18.53"	GM16	4
6. Belishka (Belichka) Reka River	1000-1600		GM05, GM14	16
7. Belichki Mochuri (near Skakavitsa Lake)	2200	42°12'42.27"; 23°18'23.00"	FM97	1
8. Belmeken Chalet, surroundings	2100-2300	42°11'33.24"; 24°44'57.01"	GM27	16
9. Belmeken Peak, surroundings	2626	42°10'49.79"; 23°46'18.05"	GM27	6
10. Belovo (above Belovo, Maritsa River)	350-400	42°12'33.11"; 24°00'33.76"	KG57	37
11. Belovo (near Golyamo Belovo, Yadenitsa River)	440	42°11'15.47"; 23°59'08.73"	GM47	6
12. Bistritsa River near Samokov (Musalenska Bistritsa River)	984	42°19'08.77"; 23°33'43.46"	GM18	3
13. Bistritsa Village, above Blagoevgrad	590	42°03'13.74"; 23°11'02.95"	FM85	16
14. Blagoevgrad Town	400-450	42°01'23.82"; 23°06'22.43"	FM75	98
15. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River	430-2050		FM75, FM85, FM95, GM05	29
16. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River, above Blagoevgrad	480	42°02'26.23"; 23°08'52.65"	FM75	11
17. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River, above Bistritsa Village	671	42°03'01.51"; 23°12'32.96"	FM85	7
18. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River near Haydushka Reka River	1568	42°02'29.48"; 23°22'36.93"	FM95	11
19. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River near Macedoniya Chalet	2003	42°02'40.00"; 23°25'02.16"	FM95, GM05	6
20. Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River (the springs)	2465	42°03'27.08"; 23°26'26.16"	GM05	3
21. Borovets Resort, surroundings	1230-1400	42°15'50.30"; 23°36'23.65"	GM18	179
22. Borovets (above Borovets)	1400-1600	42°15'34.44"; 23°36'31.96"	GM18	15
23. Brichebor Peak, surroundings	2104	42°07'10.82"; 23°21'21.83"	FM96	16
24. Chadartepa Peak	1789	42°05'07.82"; 23°48'01.16"	GM36	4
25. Chanagyolski Ezera Lakes	2216-2353		FM97	1
26. Chanagyolski Ezera – Dolen Chanak Lake	2216	42°12'05.45"; 23°19'50.90"	FM97	2
27. Chanagyolski Ezera – Goren Chanak Lake	2353	42°11'57.44"; 23°19'33.44"	FM97	6
28. Cherna Mesta River	1000-1300		GM25, GM26	19
29. Cherna Mesta River, above Yakoruda	960	42°02'14.21"; 23°42'47.64"	GM25	3
30. Chernata Skala (south-east of Borovets)	1400	42°15'40.95"; 23°28'30.22"	GM18	3
31. Cherni (Pravi) Iskar River	1060-2350		FM97, GM08	29
32. Cherni Iskar River near Govedartsi Village	1170-1200	42°15'33.13"; 23°27'54.64"	GM08	2
33. Dagonovo Village (near Belitsa Town)	820	41°57'18.46"; 23°35'36.57"	GM14	28
34. Dobro Pole (near Blagoevgradska Bistritsa River)	1350-1400	42°02'38.95"; 23°20'38.34"	FM95	3
35. Dobro Pole (near Kravarsko Dere River)	1800-2000	42°04'21.08"; 23°19'55.64"	FM96, FM95	1
36. Dolna Banya Holiday complex (above Dolna Banya, near Bistritsa River)	800-1000	42°16'05.16"; 23°43'49.70"	GM28	42
37. Dospay Village (near Samokov)	1000-1030	42°18'41.97"; 23°30'38.09"	GM08	7
38. Drushlyavitsa River	1200-2300		FM97, FM96	2
39. Dupnitsa Town, surroundings	550-650	42°15'16.35"; 23°08'01.25"	FM78	47
40. Dzhanka (col, Dolni Kuki), surroundings	2250-2335	42°07'31.26"; 23°34'49.59"	GM16	1

Table 1. Continued

Localities	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	GPS Navigation (°N, °E)	UTM Kode	Number of species
41. Dzherman River	750-2100		FM88, FM98, FM97	12
42. Eleni Vrah Peak	2654	42°10'06.17"; 23°22'02.30"	FM97	1
43. Elenski Ezera Lakes	2470-2500	42°10'20.75"; 23°22'09.66"	FM97	1
44. Eleshnitsa Chalet	2200	42°10'40.88"; 23°17'11.36"	FM87	3
45. Eleshnitsa (mountain holiday resort)	900-950	42°07'15.47"; 23°16'33.39"	FM86	6
46. Govedartsi Village, surroundings	1170-1200	42°15'33.13"; 23°27'54.64"	GM08	36
47. Granchar Chalet, surroundings	2192-2400	42°07'16.86"; 23°35'37.26"	GM16	6
48. Granchar Lake (Grancharski Ezera Lakes)	2190	42°07'11.63"; 23°35'33.65"	GM16	1
49. Grancharitsa River	1700-2190		GM16	3
50. Grancharitsa River, near Granchar Chalet	2100	42°07'28.75"; 23°35'45.99"	GM16	1
51. Ibar Peak, surroundings	2666	42°09'19.14"; 23°44'11.34"	GM27	1
52. Ibar River, surroundings	1000-1750		GM27	1
53. Iskar River, near Samokov	966	42°19'18.42"; 23°33'13.61"	GM18	2
54. Kamenitsa River	750-2300		FM86, FM87	2
55. Kirilova (Partizanska) Polyana	1350-1475	42°09'14.17"; 23°23'54.67"	FM96, FM97	53
56. Klisura Village	1000-1030	42°19'45.24"; 23°21'56.53"	FM98	2
57. Kobilino Branishte (col)	2145	42°10'27.26"; 23°27'05.81"	GM07	3
58. Kocherinovo Town, surroundings	430-450	42°05'40.97"; 23°04'29.61"	FM76	3
59. Kostenets Village (above Kostenets Village, near the Kostenski waterfall)	900	42°14'53.22"; 23°48'16.12"	GM38	44
60. Kovach (Nalbant) Peak, surroundings	2550-2634	42°06'08.00"; 23°34'21.03"	GM16	1
61. Kravarsko (Dobropolsko) Dere River	1000-2200		FM96	30
62. Leva Reka River (Gorna Leva Reka)	1800-2250		GM07	4
63. Levi Iskar River	1250-2200		GM07, GM08	15
64. Macedoniya Chalet (below the chalet)	2003	42°02'40.00"; 23°25'02.16"	FM95, GM05	5
65. Mala Tsarkva Village, above the village (near Levi Iskar River)	1400	42°14'16.21"; 23°31'09.84"	GM08	6
66. Malyovitsa Chalet, surroundings	1960	42°11'20.30"; 23°22'27.13"	FM97	47
67. Malyovitsa Peak, surroundings	2729	42°10'22.27"; 23°21'44.58"	FM97	1
68. Malyovitsa Ridge (Dalgiya Rid)	1700	42°09'00.71"; 23°21'05.39"	FM96, FM97	2
69. Malyovitsa River	1350-2350		FM97	16
70. Marichini Ezera Lakes – Dolno Lake	2368	42°09'51.70"; 23°35'45.58"	GM17	6
71. Marichini Ezera Lakes – Gorno Lake	2378	42°09'41.44"; 23°35'45.99"	GM17	5
72. Maritsa River	860-2375		GM17, GM18, GM28	1
73. Maritsa River near Belovo	340	42°13'34.94"; 23°59'19.17"	KG57	3
74. Maritsa River near Kostenets	512	42°18'36.11"; 23°50'51.44"	GM38	2
75. Maritsa River near Momina Klisura	370-380	42°13'53.40"; 23°57'36.12"	GM47	4
76. Maritsa River near Raduil Village	860-900	42°16'59.64"; 23°41'09.08"	GM28	6
77. Maritsa River near Saragyol place	1650-2000	42°13'09.14"; 23°38'34.42"	GM17	3
78. Maritsa River, springs	2370-2550		GM17	2
79. Mesta River	780-970		GM25, GM15, GM14	4
80. Mesta River (confluence of the rivers Bela and Cherna Mesta)	960	42°02'18.38"; 23°42'39.28"	GM25	3
81. Mesta River, above Yakoruda	930	42°01'52.05"; 23°41'33.18"	GM25	4
82. Mesta River, below Yakoruda	868	42°00'46.19"; 23°38'56.64"	GM15	5

Table 1. Continued

Localities	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	GPS Navigation (°N, °E)	UTM Kode	Number of species
83. Mursalevo Village	460	42°07'17.48"; 23°03'35.22"	FM66, FM76	4
84. Musala Chalet, surroundings	2100-2389	42°11'51.12"; 23°35'17.70"	GM17	31
85. Musala Peak, surroundings	2600-2925	42°10'45.20"; 23°35'06.14"	GM17	8
86. Musalenska Bistritsa River	900-2390		GM17, GM18	19
87. Musalenska Bistritsa, above Samokov	1040	42°18'09.04"; 23°34'08.51"	GM18	4
88. Musalenska Bistritsa near Samokov	980	42°19'09.53"; 23°33'42.31"	GM18	4
89. Musalenski Ezera Lakes	2389-2709		GM17	2
90. Musalenski Ezera – Alekovo Lake	2545	42°11'24.39"; 23°34'59.30"	GM17	2
91. Musalenski Ezera – Dolno Lake	2389	42°11'48.12"; 23°35'16.30"	GM17	1
92. Musalenski Ezera – Karakashevo Lake	2391	42°11'34.87"; 23°35'25.78"	GM17	1
93. Musalenski Ezera – Ledenoto Lake	2709	42°10'55.54"; 23°35'20.08"	GM17	2
94. Musalenski Ezera – No 4	2487	42°11'41.20"; 23°35'00.91"	GM17	2
95. Musalenski Ezera – No 6	2390	42°11'42.29"; 23°35'19.62"	GM17	1
96. Ovcharchenski Vodopad Waterfall	900	42°16'08.72"; 23°13'35.33"	FM88	9
97. Parangalitsa Reserve	1500-1550	42°02'32.36"; 23°22'13.62"	FM95, GM05	120
98. Parangalitsa Reserve – Field Station IBER, BAS	1550	42°02'30.52"; 23°22'34.01"	FM95	3
99. Parangalitsa, near Haydushka River	1568	42°02'29.48"; 23°22'36.93"	FM95	2
100. Pastra Village	800-1000	42°07'31.39"; 23°14'06.26"	FM86	18
101. Pazardere River	2250-2500		FM97	1
102. Pionerska Chalet	1520	42°14'05.82"; 23°20'37.34"	FM97	5
103. Predela (col, west of Razlog)	1142	41°52'54.41"; 23°20'55.39"	FM93, FM94	30
104. Predela, surroundings	850-1150	41°53'52.95"; 23°19'19.61"	FM93, FM94	45
105. Preka Reka River	1300-2400		FM97	20
106. Prodanov Rid Ridge (Prodanovska Planina)	950-1030	42°20'51.39"; 23°31'56.79"	GM09	7
107. Raduil Village (near Borovets)	800-850	42°17'15.76"; 23°41'05.31"	GM28	16
108. Ribni Ezera Chalet, surroundings	2200-2300	42°06'45.21"; 23°29'39.12"	GM06	4
109. Rila Mts. (without exact locality)	340-2925			111
110. Rila Town, surroundings	545	42°07'54.78"; 23°08'26.10"	FM76	26
111. Rila Monastery, surroundings	1147-1300	42°08'00.70"; 23°20'24.00"	FM96	226
112. Rilska Reka River	550-2235		FM76, FM86, FM96, GN06	35
113. Rilska Reka River, above Rila Monastery	1180-1250	42°08'25.61"; 23°21'11.35"	FM96	10
114. Rilska Reka River, above Rila Monastery	1360	42°09'07.97"; 23°22'49.30"	FM96	6
115. Rilska Reka River (influx of Iliyna Reka River)	1000-1200	42°06'38.05"; 23°19'00.49"	FM96	3
116. Samokov Town (above Samokov)	1000-1100	42°18'45.77"; 23°33'37.80"	GM18	16
117. Saragyol place, surroundings	2000	42°13'13.00"; 23°38'14.21"	GM17	12
118. Sedemte Ezera Lakes	2103-2535		FM97	8
119. Sedemte Ezera – Babreka Lake	2324	42°12'13.27"; 23°18'34.10"	FM97	20
120. Sedemte Ezera – Bliznaka Lake	2250	42°12'13.77"; 23°18'56.62"	FM97	22
121. Sedemte Ezera – Detelinata Lake	2228	42°12'24.97"; 23°19'04.40"	FM97	6
122. Sedemte Ezera – Dolno Lake	2103	42°12'42.87"; 23°19'34.03"	FM97	5
123. Sedemte Ezera – Okoto Lake	2440	42°12'01.13"; 23°18'24.98"	FM97	14
124. Sedemte Ezera – Ribno Ezero Lake	2196	42°12'26.89"; 23°19'23.39"	FM97	6
125. Sedemte Ezera – Salzata Lake	2535	42°18'52.00"; 23°18'40.53"	FM97	6
126. Semkovo Chalet, surroundings	1580-1750	42°03'11.86"; 23°32'00.03"	GM15	4
127. Semkovo (holiday resort)	1580	42°02'42.99"; 23°31'34.75"	GM05	5

Table 1. Continued

Localities	Altitude (m a.s.l.)	GPS Navigation (°N, °E)	UTM Kode	Number of species
128. Shirok Dol River	1060-1300	42°16'52.05"; 23°31'35.36"	GM08	2
129. Simitli Town, surroundings	360	41°53'32.11"; 23°07'26.44"	FM73, FM74	18
130. Sitnyakovo (near Borovets)	1730	42°14'48.29"; 23°36'45.70"	GM17	1
131. Sitnyakovo, surroundings	1730-2000		GM17	2
132. Skakavitsa Chalet, surroundings	1876	42°13'50.49"; 23°18'13.50"	FM97	13
133. Skakavitsa River	1500-2175		FM97	8
134. Skakavitsa Lake (Skakavishko Ezero)	2171	42°12'54.57"; 23°18'14.69"	FM97	3
135. Slavovo locality	900-1100	42°01'41.20"; 23°16'29.82"	FM85	36
136. Smradlivo Ezero Lake (Smradlyo Lake)	2300	42°07'28.09"; 23°28'32.26"	GM06	3
137. Solenoto Dere River (Solenata Voda)	1700-2300		GM17	4
138. Stobski Piramidi	630-700	42°05'33.83"; 23°07'14.14"	FM76	6
139. Struma River	330-360		FM75, FM74	1
140. Suhoto Ezero Lake	1900	42°09'58.22"; 23°25'02.27"	GM07	22
141. Tiha Rila locality	2000	42°08'03.93"; 23°28'45.32"	GM06	4
142. Treshtenik Chalet, surroundings	1700	42°04'42.97"; 23°37'52.04"	GM16	10
143. Tsarev Vrah Peak, surroundings	1800-2376	42°04'36.83"; 23°18'39.98"	FM96	1
144. Urdina Reka River	1470-2300		FM97	22
145. Urdina Reka River	1600	42°12'34.64"; 23°22'13.15"	FM97	6
146. Urdini Ezera Lakes	2278-2375		FM97	11
147. Urdini Ezera – Fourth Lake	2336	42°10'32.66"; 23°19'57.43"	FM97	1
148. Urdini Ezera – Panitsata Lake	2278	42°10'40.21"; 23°19'45.92"	FM97	1
149. Urdini Ezera – Parvo Lake	2375	42°10'28.10"; 23°19'44.57"	FM97	2
150. Urdini Ezera – Ribno (Damgsko) Lake	2338	42°11'10.41"; 23°13'31.32"	FM97	1
151. Urdini Ezera – Triagalnika Lake	2339	42°10'44.10"; 23°19'22.18"	FM97	3
152. Urdini Ezera – Sixth Lake	2295	42°11'07.04"; 23°20'01.19"	FM97	2
153. Vada Chalet, surroundings	1410-1500	42°13'42.29"; 23°21'47.43"	FM97	10
154. Vodniya Chal (above Rilska Reka)	1850	42°08'28.65"; 23°26'38.53"	FM96	8
155. Votrachka Reka River	800-1300		GM14, GM15	15
156. Yakoruda Town, surroundings	930-1000	42°02'15.54"; 23°40'32.01"	GM25	17
157. Yakorudsko Ribno Ezero Lake	2200	42°06'05.70"; 23°35'17.93"	GM16	1
158. Yundola (col, northwest of Velinograd)	1374	42°03'42.98"; 23°51'08.62"	GM36	89
159. Zavrachitsa Chalet	2178	42°10'06.76"; 23°38'24.54"	GM17	2
160. Zhabokrek, near Rilska Reka River	580-660	42°07'47.99"; 23°09'46.68"	FM86	18

Palaeartic-Oriental, **poa** – Palaeartic-Oriental-Australian, **ppt** – Palaeartic-Paleotropical, **ppta** – Palaeartic-Paleotropical-Australian, **ptm** – Paleotropical-Mediterranean, **se** – South European, **see** – South-East European, **sena** – South European-North African, **sess** – South European and South Siberian, **sk** – Semicosmopolitan, **sp** – South Palaeartic, **spat** – South Palaeartic-Afrotropical, **sppta** – South Palaeartic-Paleotropical-Australian, **tp** – Transpalaeartic, **wces** – West and Central Eurosiberian, **wcp** – West and Central Palaeartic, **wes** – West Eurosiberian, **wesanca** – West Eurosiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian, **wesca** –

West Eurosiberian-Central Asian, **wesit** – West Eurosiberian-Iran-Turanian, **wp** – West Palaeartic, **wpat** – West Palaeartic-Afrotropical, **wpo** – West Palaeartic-Oriental.

Results and Discussion

A total of 1003 dipteran species (25.1% of the species found in Bulgaria) belonging to 58 families have been established in the Rila Mts. so far (Tables 2 and 3). The family Tachinidae is the most numerous – 162, followed by Syrphidae – 149, Cecidomyiidae – 65, Limoniidae – 62, Chloropidae – 61, Muscidae

– 55, Chironomidae – 53 and Agromyzidae – 48. The remaining families contain from one to 37 species. The taxa distribution in most cases is connected with the exploration of the corresponding mountain region. This is evident when comparing the established species with regard to localities (Table 1). Five areas of detailed research (over 80 species found) are outlined. First are the surroundings of the Rila Monastery (266 species) and Borovets (179 species) – the most visited places of the mountain. The popular starting points for entering the Rila Mts., Blagoevgrad and Yundola (89-98 species), also form a group of well-studied regions. The Parangalitsa Reserve (120 species) where there is a research base of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences is also well-studied. Regarding the other parts of the mountains, the surroundings of Belovo, Kostenets, Dolna Banya, Govedartsı Village, Dupnitsa and the Predela Area (from 36 to 47 species) are better studied. Of the inner parts of the mountains, the surroundings of Kravarsko Dere River, Kirilova Polyana, the valley of Rilska Reka River, the Slavovo Area and the chalets Malyovitsa and Musala (from 30 to 53 species) are better studied. It is seen that the localities from which the material is collected, are concentrated around the popular tourist centres or routes (when they are not near the chalets). Significant parts of the mountains are unexplored and material is not collected. This relates both to difficulties when approaching the terrain and the insufficient studies of the separate families. The number of the established species probably represents about 50-60% of the actual species composition of the studied territory. The dipterans are a highly mobile group and after further studies on the Rila Mts. can be expected to reach over 2000 species or 55-65% of the species composition of the most families found in the country.

A total of 564 species (56.23%) have been established in the protected areas of the Rila Mts. (Rila National Park – 379 species and Rila Monastery Nature Park – 304 species). In comparison with the Central Balkan National Park [184 species (HUBENOV et al., 2000a)], East Rhodopes [279 species (HUBENOV, 2004)], Vitosha Mt. [1000 species (HUBENOV, 2014)] and Pirin National Park [557 species (HUBENOV 2015b)], the dipteran fauna of the Rila Mts. is commensurable with the fauna of the Pirin Mts. The number of taxa recorded from the Rila Mts. significantly exceeds the one of the Central Balkan National Park and the East Rhodopes, and decreases vis-a-vis Vitosha Mt. It should be kept in mind that Vitosha is the most studied Bulgarian mountain and its whole territory is used for comparison (not only the Vitosha Nature Park) while

the Central Balkan National Park is poorly investigated with respect to the two-winged insects. When comparing the whole mountain with the Vitosha Mt., there is no difference in the number of the established species. The last studies on Diptera of the Pirin Mts. (HUBENOV 2015b) allow the fauna families to be compared with these of the Rila Mts. The great number of species, established in the Rila Monastery Nature Park is related to the fact that the surroundings of the Rila Monastery are the most visited region of the Rila Mts. (Table 1). Under further exploration, the Rila Mts. are expected to be similar to the most of the Bulgarian high mountains in terms of species composition of Diptera. This relates to the natural habitats of the mountain, as well as to the wide distribution of the dipterans, their high mobility and poorly expressed endemism.

In the xerothermic oak forests belt 256 species (25.5%) have been established, despite its limited development in the north-eastern, western and south-western parts of the mountain. This is connected with the open spaces to which species of the contiguous valleys penetrate. Most species have been found in beech forests (736 species – 74.4%), and mesophilic and xeromesophilic mixed forests (351 species – 35.0%). The border between beech and coniferous forests of the Rila Mts. is not clear and depending on the exposure, relief and anthropogenic impact, there are wide areas of mixing (200-300 m a.s.l.). This determines the high species richness in the beech belt, the great number of common species and the similarity of the dipteran fauna among the second, third and fourth vegetation belts. Regarding the hypsometric belts, the maximum number of species is recorded between 1000 and 1500 m a.s.l. The upper limit of the coniferous zone gradually passes into the subalpine vegetation zones with a mixture of regions at about 200 m a.s.l. Thus, most of the species are common to both vegetation belts and the number of taxa established in the subalpine belt increases. Among the species found in the alpine belt, *Molophilus lautereri* Stary (Bulgarian endemic of Limoniidae), *Micropsectra radialis* Goet. (Palearctic-Oriental species of Chironomidae), *Eudorylas jenkinsoni* Coe (European species of Pipunculidae) and *Didea alneti* Fall. (Holarctic species of Syrphidae) are typical only for this belt. All other species have been established in the subalpine belt and most of them – in the other vegetation belts as well. In some cases, the finding of species at certain altitude takes place accidentally. The lack of systematic research on Diptera of the Rila Mts. and the fragmentary data for most families do not allow explicit conclusions about the adherence of the taxa to one or another vegeta-

Table 2. Two-winged insects (Insecta: Diptera) of the Rila Mts.

Families	Total species number of the two parks		Species of the Rila National Park		Species of the Rila Monastery Nature Park		Species of Rila Mts.	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
NEMATOCERA	188	33.33	128	33.77	109	35.85	294	29.31
Tipulidae	7	1.24	3	0.79	7	2.30	9	0.90
Limoniidae	49	8.69	22	5.80	31	10.20	62	6.18
Pediciidae	10	1.77	6	1.58	6	1.97	13	1.30
Blephariceridae	1	0.18	1	0.26			2	0.20
Bibionidae	2	0.35			2	0.66	4	0.40
Mycetophilidae	9	1.60	8	2.11	3	0.99	14	1.40
Bolitophilidae	4	0.71	4	1.06			4	0.40
Diadocidiidae	1	0.18	1	0.26	1	0.33	1	0.10
Keroplastidae	2	0.35	1	0.26	2	0.66	3	0.30
Macroceridae	2	0.35			2	0.66	4	0.40
Sciaridae	4	0.71	1	0.26	4	0.32	4	0.40
Cecidomyiidae	18	3.19	3	0.79	17	5.59	65	6.48
Trichoceridae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Scatopsidae	1	0.18			1	0.33	1	0.10
Ptychopteridae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Culicidae	3	0.53	2	0.53	1	0.33	9	0.90
Simuliidae	35	6.21	34	8.97	29	9.54	37	3.69
Ceratopogonidae	2	0.35	2	0.53			6	0.60
Chironomidae	38	6.74	38	10.03	3	0.99	53	5.28
BRACHYCERA ORTHORRHAPHA	43	7.62	33	8.71	19	6.25	108	10.77
Coenomyiidae	1	0.18			1	0.33	1	0.10
Stratiomyidae	2	0.35			2	0.66	5	0.50
Rhagionidae	4	0.71	4	1.05	2	0.66	5	0.50
Tabanidae	20	3.55	20	5.28	1	0.33	25	2.49
Bombyliidae	4	0.71	3	0.79	4	0.32	9	0.90
Therevidae							2	0.20
Asilidae	7	1.24	3	0.79	6	1.97	23	2.29
Empididae	3	0.53	1	0.26	3	0.99	8	0.80
Hybotidae							5	0.50
Dolichopodidae	2	0.35	2	0.53			25	2.49
BRACHYCERA CYCLORRHAPHA	333	59.04	218	75.52	176	57.89	601	59.92
Platypezidae							1	0.10
Phoridae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Pipunculidae	3	0.53	2	0.53	1	0.33	5	0.50
Syrphidae	76	13.47	53	13.98	31		149	14.86
Conopidae	8	1.42	4	1.05	6	1.97	20	1.99
Tephritidae	5	0.89	1	0.26	4	0.32	8	0.80
Lauxaniidae							1	0.10
Cremifaniidae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Chamaemyiidae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Sciomyzidae	1	0.18			1	0.33	2	0.20

Table 2. Continued

Families	Total species number of the two parks		Species of the Rila National Park		Species of the Rila Monastery Nature Park		Species of Rila Mts.	
	number	%	number	%	number	%	number	%
Agromyzidae	33	5.85			33	10.85	48	4.79
Opomyzidae	2	0.35	2	0.53			2	0.20
Milichiidae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Chloropidae	39	6.91	35	9.23	10	3.29	61	6.08
Heleomyzidae	2	0.35	2	0.53			2	0.20
Sphaeroceridae	2	0.35	2	0.53			2	0.20
Drosophilidae	1	0.18			1	0.33	1	0.10
Diastatidae	1	0.18	1	0.26			1	0.10
Ephydriidae	22	3.90	22	5.80	3	0.99	26	2.59
Hippoboscidae	1	0.18	1	0.26	1	0.33	2	0.20
Scathophagidae	2	0.35	2	0.53			2	0.20
Anthomyiidae	2	0.35	2	0.53			3	0.30
Fanniidae	2	0.35	2	0.53	2	0.66	2	0.20
Muscidae	38	6.74	35	9.23	11	3.62	55	5.48
Calliphoridae	8	1.42	3	0.79	6	1.97	14	1.40
Sarcophagidae	14	2.48	2	0.53	12	3.95	24	2.39
Rhinophoridae							1	0.10
Gasterophilidae							3	0.30
Tachinidae	67	11.88	43	11.34	54	17.76	162	16.15
Families	52	89.65	44	75.86	36	62.07	58	
Species	564	56.23	379	37.79	304	30.31	1003	

tion zone to be made. The distribution of species in groups according to their presence in the vegetation belts has a relative character and depends on the specific features of taxa and research area, as well as on the duration of the research. There is a correlation between the horizontal and vertical distribution of Diptera. Species found in the subalpine and alpine zones (above 2200 – 2500 m a.s.l.), have large areals, and are with mainly Palaearctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, West Palaearctic, Holoeurosiberian or European distribution (Table 3). There are considerable differences between the Pirin and Rila Mountains (from 11.3% to 18.3%) in the number of species in the first three vegetation belts (especially the beech belt). They are probably related to the specific climatic conditions of the two mountains and the insufficient research on most of the families.

The zoogeographical categorisation of the species (Table 3) is made on the basis of current data about their distribution. Thus, the dipterans are divided into 84 areographical categories, combined into two main groups and six subgroups (Table 4).

Species distributed in the Palaearctic and

beyond it. This group (258 species – 25.7%) includes 26 categories, of which 23 combine species of northern type (widely distributed in the Holarctic and Palaearctic) and three with species of southern type (distributed only in the southern parts of the Palaearctic). The difference between the separate vegetation belts with respect to this group is from 0.4 to 16.1% (from 11 to 196 species). In the first five vegetation belts the difference is minimal (not exceeding 5.1%) and increases in the alpine belt where the species with vast areas dominate. It is very likely the establishment of other species of the group of the northern type in the last two vegetation belts of the Rila Mts. owing to their distribution and insufficient studies of the higher parts of the mountain. It is accepted that the species of the northern type have vast areas and ecological flexibility. In the Superpalaearctic complex, the Holarctic species (124 species – 12.4%) prevail and as compared to the other areographical categories where the Holarctic-Oriental (31 species – 3.1%) and the Palaearctic-Oriental forms (29 species – 2.9%) are better presented (Table 4). The species of the southern type are

Table 3. Species composition and distribution of the two-winged insects (Insecta: Diptera) of the Rila Mts.

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
NEMATOCERA					
TIPULOMORPHA					
Tipulidae / 9					
<i>Tanyptera atrata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111	◆	1147	tp, ? hoes	102
<i>Nephrotoma cornicina</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111	◆	1147	ho	169
<i>Tipula (Acutipula) maxima</i> Poda, 1761	111	◆	1147	ena	102
<i>Tipula (Lunatipula) lunata</i> Linnaeus, 1758	111	◆	1147	hoes	102
<i>Tipula (Lunatipula) vernalis</i> Meigen, 1804	23, 39, 109, 111, 140	◆◆	550-2100	e	102
<i>Tipula (Vestiplex) excisa</i> Schummel, 1833	109	◆◆	550-2900	hoes	145, 169
<i>Tipula (Vestiplex) nubeculosa</i> Meigen, 1804	21	◆◆	1350	eca	145
<i>Tipula (Vestiplex) scripta</i> Meigen, 1830	23, 39, 109, 111, 140	◆◆	550-2100	wces	102
<i>Tipula (Yamatotipula) montium</i> Egger, 1863	21	◆◆	1350	wces	145
Limoniidae / 62					
<i>Phyllolabis pubipennis</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	84	●	2389	csee	122
<i>Paradelphomyia (Oxyrhiza) fuscata</i> (Loew, 1873)	111	◆	1147	eit	120
<i>Austrolimnophila (Archilimnophila) unica</i> (Osten Sacken, 1869)	132	●	1876	h	120
<i>Epiphragma (Epiphragma) ocellare</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	111	◆	1147	h	120
<i>Elocophila maculata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	111	◆	1147	et	120
<i>Elocophila mundata</i> (Loew, 1871)	84	●	2389	e	119
<i>Elocophila trimaculata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	84	●	2389	e	119, 121
<i>Euphyllidorea lineola</i> (Meigen, 1804)	84	●	2389	wp	119, 122
<i>Neolimnomyia (Brachylimnophila) nemoralis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	84, 111, 132	●	1147-2389	tp	119, 120, 122
<i>Phyllidorea (Paraphyllidorea) fulvonervosa</i> (Schummel, 1829)	132	●	1876	des	120
<i>Phyllidorea (Phyllidorea) ferruginea</i> (Meigen, 1818)	142	●	1700	esca	119, 157
<i>Prionolabis hospes</i> (Egger, 1863)	84, 112, 132	◆◆	1360-2389	cse	119, 120, 122, 139
<i>Pseudolimnophila (Pseudolimnophila) lucorum</i> (Meigen, 1818)	111	◆	1147	esca	119, 169
<i>Pseudolimnophila (Pseudolimnophila) sepium</i> (Verrall, 1886)	111	◆	1147	eit	120
<i>Hexatoma (Hexatoma) bicolor</i> (Meigen, 1818)	111	◆	1147	csea	120

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Chionea (Sphaeconophilus) lutescens</i> Lundstrom, 1907	117	•	2000	XI-IV 48, 119
<i>Crypteria limnophiloides</i> Bergroth, 1913	21		1230-1390	VIII-X 119
<i>Neolimnophila carteri</i> (Tonnoir, 1921)	84, 142	•	1700-2389	VI 119, 121, 157
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) divisa</i> (Walker, 1848)	84, 142	•	1700-2389	VII 121, 157
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) flavata</i> (Westhoff, 1882)	142		1700	V-VI 157
<i>Erioptera (Erioptera) lutea</i> Meigen, 1804	111, 132	•	1147-1876	VI-VII 120
<i>Erioptera (Mesocyphona) bivittata</i> (Loew, 1873)	84	•	2389	VI-VII 121
<i>Scleroprocta balcanica</i> Stary, 1976	111	♦	1147	VI, VIII 120
<i>Symplecta (Symplecta) hybrida</i> (Meigen, 1804)	156		930-1000	V-VIII, X 119, 157
<i>Cheilotrichia (Empeda) staryi</i> Mendl, 1973	21		1230-1390	VIII-IX 119
<i>Eriocnopa trivialis</i> (Meigen, 1818)	84	•	2389	VIII 121
<i>Hoplolabis (Parilisia) yezoana</i> (Alexander, 1924)	113	♦	1180-1250	VII-VIII 120
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) appendiculatus</i> (Staeger, 1840)	21		1230-1390	VIII-IX 119
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) bifidus</i> Goetghebuer, 1920	111	♦	1147	VI 120
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) crassipygus</i> Meijere, 1918	111, 113	♦	1147-1250	VIII 119, 120
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) directidens</i> Stary, 1976	21, 111	♦♦	1147-1450	VIII-IX 119, 160
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) flagellatus</i> Stary, 1976	21		1230-1390	VIII-IX 119
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) lackschewitzianus</i> Alexander, 1953	109			VII 119
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) lautereri</i> Stary, 1974	51	•	2666	VI 139
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) medius</i> Meijere, 1918	111, 142	♦	1147-1700	VI-VIII 119, 139
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) obscurus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	111, 142	♦	1147-1700	VI, VIII 119, 157, 169
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) obsoletus</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	84	•	2389	VI-VII 119, 121
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) propinquus</i> (Egger, 1863)	111, 142	♦	1147-1700	VI, VIII-IX 120, 157
<i>Molophilus (Molophilus) scutellatus</i> Goetghebuer, 1929	84	•	2389	VIII 119, 121, 157
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) albitibia</i> Edwards, 1921	21		1230-1390	IX 119
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) clavata</i> (Tonnoir, 1920)	21		1230-1390	IX 119
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) fascipennis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	84	•	2389	VI 119, 121, 157
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) pirinensis</i> Stary, 1971	21		1230-1390	VI, IX 120

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Ormosia (Ormosia) staegeriana</i> Alexander, 1953	21		1230-1390	e	VIII-IX 119
<i>Rhyphotophus haemorrhoidalis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	21, 55, 111, 154	◆	1147-1850	e	VIII-IX 119, 120, 169
<i>Rhyphotophus obtusistyla</i> (Stary, 1976)	55, 111, 154	◆	1147-1850	Ebg	VIII 119, 160
<i>Dicranoptycha livescens</i> Loew, 1871	111	◆	1147-1250	cse	VIII 119, 169
<i>Dicranoptycha paralivescens</i> Stary, 1972	111	◆	1147-1250	cse	VII-VIII 120
<i>Lipsothrix errans</i> (Walker, 1848)	111	◆	1147	e	VI 120
<i>Lipsothrix remota</i> (Walker, 1848)	111	◆	1147	e	VI 120
<i>Antocha (Orimargula) alpigena</i> (Mik, 1883)	55, 111, 154	◆	1147-1850	csea	VI, VIII 120
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) luteipennis</i> Goetghebuer, 1920	55, 111	◆	1147-1475	cse	VIII 120
<i>Dicranomyia (Dicranomyia) mitis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	111, 111, 154	◆	1147-1850	wp	VI, VIII 120
<i>Discobola annulata</i> (Linnaeus 1758)	111, 113	◆	1147-1250	hoa	VIII 120
<i>Limonia flavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	111	◆	1147	ena	VI 120
<i>Limonia macrostigma</i> (Schummel, 1829)	111, 113	◆	1147-1250	po	VI, VIII 120
<i>Limonia phragmitidis</i> (Schränk, 1781)	111	◆	1147	wp	V-VI 120
<i>Limonia sylvicola</i> (Schummel, 1829)	21, 111, 113, 114, 154	◆◆	1147-1850	wces	VIII-IX 119, 120
<i>Limonia trivittata</i> (Schummel, 1829)	21		1230-1390	esca	VII-IX 119, 145
<i>Metalmobia (Metalmobia) zetterstedti</i> (Tjeder, 1968)	132	●	1876	hoes	VI-VIII 120
<i>Neolimonia dumetorum</i> (Meigen, 1804)	68, 111	◆	1174-1700	e	VI, VIII 120
<i>Rhipidia (Rhipidia) maculata</i> Meigen, 1818	21, 111, 114	◆	1147-1390	h	VI, VIII 119, 120
Pediciidae / 13					
<i>Dicranota (Dicranota) bimaculata</i> (Schummel, 1829)	132	●	1876	wp	VII 120
<i>Dicranota (Ludicia) lucidipennis</i> (Edwards, 1921)	111, 132	◆◆	1174-1876	cse	VI-VII 120
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) brevicornis</i> Bergroth, 1891	132	●	1876	cse	VII 120
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) flammifera</i> Stary, 1981	111	◆	1147	cse	VI 120
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) pallens</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	84, 132	●	1876-2389	csee	VII 119, 120, 122
<i>Dicranota (Paradicranota) simulans</i> Lackschewitz, 1940	111	◆	1147	csea	VI 120
<i>Pedicia (Amalopsis) occulta</i> (Meigen, 1830)	21, 55, 84, 111	◆◆	1147-2389	eswa	VI, VIII 119, 120, 122
<i>Pedicia (Crunobia) littoralis</i> (Meigen, 1804)	111	◆	1147	e	VI 120

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Pedicia (Crunobia) riedeli</i> (Lackschewitz, 1940)	113	◆	1250	139
<i>Pedicia (Pedicia) rivosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1230-1390	119
<i>Pedicia (Crunobia) spinifera</i> Stary, 1974	132	●	1876	120, 158
<i>Tricyphona (Tricyphona) livida</i> Madarassy, 1881	21		1230-1390	119
<i>Ula (Ula) mollissima</i> Haliday 1833	21		1230-1390	119
BLEPHARICEROMORPHA				
Blephariceridae / 2				
<i>Blepharicera fasciata</i> (Westwood, 1842)	63, 65		1400	1
<i>Liponeura cinerascens</i> Loew, 1844	21, 65, 85	●	1230-2925	114
BIBIONOMORPHA				
Bibionidae / 4				
<i>Bibio hortulanus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111	◆	1147	102
<i>Bibio lanigerus</i> Meigen, 1818	23, 39, 110, 111, 140	◆	550-2100	102
<i>Bibio marci</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	10		400	145
<i>Bibio pomonae</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	36		850-1000	52
Mycetophilidae / 14				
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) cinerascens</i> (Macquart, 1826)	21		1230-1390	15
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) disa</i> Vaisanen, 1984	22	●	1450	9, 15
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) prominens</i> (Lundström, 1913)	156		930-1000	14, 175
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) ruficollis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1852)	22	●	1450	7, 15
<i>Mycomya (Mycomya) tenuis</i> (Walker, 1856)	22	●	1450	15
<i>Boletina gripha</i> Dziedziński, 1885	84	●	2389	15
<i>Boletina sciarina</i> Staeger, 1840	116		1000-1100	8, 15
<i>Leia winthemii</i> Lehmann, 1822	21		1230-1390	15
<i>Novakia scatopsiformis</i> Strobl, 1893	21		1230-1390	15
<i>Cordyla murina</i> Winnertz, 1863	109	●	2200	15
<i>Exechia fusca</i> (Meigen, 1804)	23, 39, 110, 111, 140	◆	550-2100	15, 102
<i>Exechiopsis (Exechiopsis) clypeata</i> (Lundstrom, 1911)	84	●	2389	15

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical		
<i>Sceptonia membranacea</i> Edwards, 1925	97, 111	◆◆	1147-1524	e	VII-IX	15
<i>Sceptonia pilosa</i> Bukowski, 1934	111	◆	1147	e	VI-IX	15
Bolitophilidae / 4						
<i>Bolitophila (Bolitophila) cinerea</i> Meigen, 1818	97	●	1500	hoes	VI-VIII	11, 13
<i>Bolitophila (Bolitophila) saundersii</i> (Curtis, 1836)	97	●	1500	tp	V-XI	11, 13
<i>Bolitophila (Bolitophila) tenella</i> Winnertz, 1863	97	●	1500	des	VIII	10, 13
<i>Bolitophila (Cliopisa) hybrida</i> (Meigen, 1804)	109	●		hoes	VII	145
Diadocidiidae / 1						
<i>Diadocidia (Diadocidia) spinosula</i> Tollef, 1948	97, 111	◆◆	1147-1500	e	VI-IX	11, 13
Keroplattidae / 3						
<i>Antlemon (Antlemonopsis) brevimanum</i> (Loew, 1871)	21, 55, 97	◆◆	1147-1500	cse, ? csee	VIII-IX	11, 13
<i>Orfelia unicolor</i> (Stæger, 1840)	55	◆	1475	hoes	V-IX	11, 13
<i>Platyura marginata</i> Meigen, 1804	59		900	des	V-VI	11, 13
Macroceridae / 4						
<i>Macrocera centralis</i> Meigen, 1818	55	◆	1350-1450	wes	V-IX	11, 13
<i>Macrocera grandis</i> Lundström, 1912	111	◆	1150	cee	VIII	12, 13
<i>Macrocera inversa</i> Loew, 1869	21		1300	wes	V-VII	11, 13
<i>Macrocera stigmoides</i> Edwards, 1925	21		1300	e	V-VIII	11, 13
Sciariidae / 4						
<i>Phytosciara (Phytosciara) halterata</i> (Lengersdorf, 1926)	111	◆	1150	e	VIII	44
<i>Sciara analis</i> Schiner, 1864	23, 39, 109, 111, 140	◆◆	550-2100	csee	IV-X	102
<i>Sciara hemerobioides</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	110, 111	◆	545-1150	po	VI-IX	102; 145
<i>Phytosciara (Phytosciara) macrotricha</i> (Lengersdorf, 1926)	111	◆	1150	cee	VIII	44
Cecidomyiidae / 65						
<i>Lasioptera eryngii</i> (Vallot, 1829)	33		850-900	ena	V-VI	154
<i>Lasioptera rubi</i> (Schrank, 1803)	36, 59		800-1000	des	V-VII	73, 45, 146
<i>Bayeriola capitigena</i> (Bremi, 847)	33, 103, 107		850-1150	e	V-IX	154
<i>Bayeriola thymicola</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	14, 33		400-900	ena	VI-VIII	154

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Dasineura acrophila</i> (Winnertz 1853)	33		850	h	154
<i>Dasineura asperulae</i> (Löw, 1875)	33		850	cse	154
<i>Dasineura crataegi</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	21, 107		800-1300	e	142, 154
<i>Dasineura fraxinea</i> Kieffer, 1907	33		850	e	154
<i>Dasineura galicicola</i> (Löw, 1880)	104		1150	e	154
<i>Dasineura hyperici</i> (Brems, 1848)	104, 107		800-1150	e	154
<i>Dasineura irregularis</i> (Brems, 1847)	111	◆	1200	cse	154
<i>Dasineura medicaginis</i> (Brems, 1847)	33		850	wes	154
<i>Dasineura papaveris</i> (Winnertz, 1890)	14, 33		400-850	cseca	154
<i>Dasineura plicatrix</i> (Loew, 1850)	14		400	ena	154
<i>Dasineura pteridicola</i> (Kieffer 1901)	33		850	wes	154
<i>Dasineura pyri</i> (Bouché 1847)	14		400	ha	154
<i>Dasineura rosae</i> (Brems, 1847)	14, 33, 107, 111	◆◆	400-1200	dp, ? h	154
<i>Dasineura rossi</i> Rübtsaamen, 1914	33		850	wes	154
<i>Dasineura schulzei</i> (Rübtsaamen, 1917)	103		1150	csee	154
<i>Dasineura tortilis</i> (Brems, 1847)	103		1150	e	154
<i>Dasineura tortrix</i> (Löw, 1877)	14, 33, 103, 111	◆	400-1200	e	154
<i>Dasineura trifolii</i> (Löw, 1874)	33, 103		900-1150	h	154
<i>Dasineura urticae</i> (Perris, 1840)	33, 103		900-1150	des	154
<i>Euphorbomyia loewii</i> (Mik, 1882)	14		400	csee	154
<i>Rabdophaga heterobia</i> (Loew, 1850)	103		1150	dp	154
<i>Rabdophaga terminalis</i> (Loew, 1850)	103		1150	tp	154
<i>Geocrypta galii</i> (Loew, 1850)	103, 111	◆	1100-1200	des	154
<i>Gephyraulus raphanistri</i> (Kieffer, 1886)	107		800	e	154
<i>Hartigiola annulipes</i> (Hartig, 1839)	107, 111	◆	800-1200	dp	142, 154
<i>Iteomyia capreae</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	104		1150	tp	154
<i>Jaapiella bryoniae</i> (Bouche, 1847)	33		900	ena	154
<i>Jaapiella jaapiana</i> (Rübtsaamen, 1914)	14		400	e	154

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Jaapiella veronicae</i> (Vallot, 1827)	104, 107, 111	◆	800-1200	e	154
<i>Janetiella fallax</i> Kieffer, 1904	33		850-900	e	154
<i>Janetiella lemeei</i> (Kieffer, 1904)	14		400	ean	154
<i>Janetiella thymi</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	103		1150	e	154
<i>Macrolabis heraclei</i> Kaltenbach, 1862	111	◆	1150	e	154
<i>Mayetiola poae</i> (Bosc, 1817)	109			e	142
<i>Phegomyia fagicola</i> (Kieffer, 1901)	103		1150	e	154
<i>Physemocelis ulmi</i> (Kieffer, 1909)	14, 111	◆	400-1150	e	154
<i>Mikiola fagi</i> (Hartig, 1839)	104, 107, 111	◆◆	800-1200	e, ? des	142, 154
<i>Mikomya coryli</i> (Kieffer, 1901)	33, 111		850-1150	ean	154
<i>Oligotrophus juniperinus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	33, 43	●	850-2500	e	142, 154
<i>Oligotrophus panteli</i> (Kieffer, 1898)	33		850-900	ena	154
<i>Rhopalomyia foliorum</i> (Loew, 1850)	33		850-900	e	154
<i>Semudobia betulae</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	14, 33, 103, 107, 111	◆◆	400-1150	h	154
<i>Wachtliella stachydis</i> (Bremer, 1847)	103		1150	e	154
<i>Zygobia carpini</i> (Löw, 1874)	104, 111	◆	1100-1200	e	154
<i>Asphonodylia hornigi</i> Wachtl, 1880	107		800	e	154
<i>Acodiplois inulae</i> (Loew, 1847)	59		900	e	154
<i>Aschistonyx carpinicolus</i> Rübtsaamen, 1917	103, 111	◆	1100-1150	e	154
<i>Contarinia carpini</i> Kieffer, 1897	111	◆	1200	e	154
<i>Contarinia coryli</i> (Kaltenbach, 1859)	107		800	esca	154
<i>Contarinia crataegi</i> Loew, 1850	14		400	wes	154
<i>Contarinia fagi</i> Rübtsaamen, 1921	104, 107		800-1100	e	154
<i>Contarinia geti</i> Kieffer, 1909	111	◆	1200	e	154
<i>Contarinia hypochoeridis</i> (Rübtsaamen 1891)	33		850-900	e	154
<i>Contarinia lamii</i> Kieffer, 1909	111	◆	1140	e	154
<i>Contarinia nasturtii</i> (Kieffer, 1888)	33, 104, 107		800-1100	ean	154
<i>Contarinia steini</i> (Karsch, 1881)	111	◆	1140	e	154

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Drisina glutinosa</i> Giard, 1893	111	◆	1200	e	154
<i>Harmandiola cavernosa</i> (Rübsaamen, 1899)	30		1400	wes	142
<i>Harmandiola globuli</i> (Rübsaamen, 1889)	30		1400	wes	142
<i>Harmandiola tremulae</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	30		1400	wes	142
<i>Mycodiplosis contiohaga</i> (Winnertz, 1853)	111	◆	1140	h	154
<i>Putoniella pruni</i> Kaltenbach, 1872	14, 33		400-850	e	154
Trichoceridae / 1					
<i>Trichocera (Trichocera) hiemalis</i> (De Geer, 1776)	117	●	2000	h	II, X 48
Scatopsidae / 1					
<i>Colobostema nigripenne</i> (Meigen, 1830)	23, 111,	◆	1150-1500	ena	65
Ptychopteridae / 1					
<i>Ptychoptera (Ptychoptera) scutellaris</i> Meigen, 1818	8	●	2100	h	7
CULICOMORPHA					
Culicidae / 9					
<i>Anopheles (Anopheles) maculipennis</i> Meigen, 1818	157	●	2190-2200	wesit	III-X 43, 136
<i>Culiseta (Culiseta) annulata</i> (Schränk, 1776)	21		1230-1390	ena	VI-IX 42, 43
<i>Culiseta (Culiseta) glaphyoptera</i> (Schiner, 1864)	21		1230-1390	csee, m	VIII-IX 43
<i>Ochlerotatus (Ochlerotatus) communis</i> (De Geer, 1776)	21		1230-1390	h	VII 42
<i>Ochlerotatus (Ochlerotatus) pullatus</i> (Coquillett, 1904)	21, 84	●	1230-2300	h, ba	VI-VII 42
<i>Ochlerotatus (Ochlerotatus) punctator</i> (Kirby, 1837)	21		1230-1390	h	VII 42
<i>Ochlerotatus (Finlaya) gemiculatus</i> (Olivier, 1791)	21		1230-1390	wp	V-VII 42
<i>Culex (Culex) pipiens</i> Linnaeus, 1758	21, 23, 39, 110, 111, 140	◆	550-2100	hnat	IV-XI 102, 42
<i>Culex (Maillotia) hortensis</i> Ficalbi 1889	21		1230-1390	wpo	VI-VII, X 42
Simuliidae / 37					
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) fulvipes</i> (Edwards, 1921)	5, 15, 31, 47, 49, 55, 63, 86, 105, 112, 117, 144	◆◆	1300-2400	cseea	VII 64, 116, 117
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) hirtipes</i> (Fries, 1824)	3, 5, 15, 24, 27, 31, 47, 49, 63, 84, 105, 112, 119, 120, 122, 123, 144	◆◆	1300-2450	tp, ? h	VIII 116, 117, 145, 163

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution					References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	Fenology	
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) latimicro</i> (Enderlein, 1925)	2, 15, 31, 47, 77, 105, 112, 120, 123, 144	◆◆	1200-2400	e	V-VI	116, 117
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) petrosum</i> Rubtsov, 1955	112	◆	1100-2235	see		115, 117
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) rufipes</i> (Meigen, 1830)	2, 15, 31, 62, 63, 69, 72, 105, 111, 112, 117, 144	◆◆	1300-2300	ena	V-VII	64, 116, 117
<i>Prosimulium (Prosimulium) tomosvaryi</i> (Enderlein, 1921)	2, 31, 82, 86	●	850-2000	des	V, X	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) angustitarse</i> (Lundstrom 1911)	3, 41, 86	●	1000-1700	dp	IV, XI	117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) bertrandi</i> Grenier et Dorier, 1959	31, 55, 63, 69, 105, 112, 117, 119, 144	◆◆	1950-2300	e	VI-VII	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) brevidens</i> (Rubtsov, 1956)	2, 6, 15, 28, 31, 69, 82, 105, 119, 121, 133, 155	◆◆	450-2350	e	VII	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) carpathicum</i> (Knoz, 1961)	2, 15, 31, 69, 105, 112, 133, 144, 155	●	400-2000	e	VII-VIII	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) carthusiense</i> Grenier & Dorier, 1959	2, 6, 15, 28, 31, 41, 69, 105, 112, 117, 144, 155	◆◆	1000-2300	e		117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) codreanui</i> (Serban, 1958)	15, 28, 38, 47, 55, 63, 105, 112, 117	◆◆	1300-2150	e	VII-VIII	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) costatum</i> Friederichs, 1920	2, 15, 28, 63, 105, 133, 145	◆◆	1100-2300	ena	V-VIII	117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) crenobium</i> (Knoz, 1961)	2, 15, 31, 55, 63, 101, 105, 112, 117, 144	◆◆	1400	csee	VI-VII	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) cryophilum</i> (Rubzov, 1959)	2, 6, 15, 28, 69, 82, 105, 107, 112, 133, 155	◆◆	750-2200	ena	VI-IX	116
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) curvans</i> (Rubtsov & Carlsson, 1965)	31, 69, 112, 144	◆◆	1200-2100	hoes		115, 117
<i>Simulium (Nevermannia) latigonia</i> (Rubzov, 1956)	6, 41, 86	●	1100-2000	e	IV, VII, XI	117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) argenteostratum</i> Strobl, 1898	2, 3, 6, 15, 28, 62, 112, 131, 155	◆◆	700-2100	? csena	V-IX	64, 116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) argyreatum</i> Meigen, 1838	2, 6, 15, 28, 31, 41, 63, 69, 76, 80, 105, 112, 133, 155	◆◆	400-2400	e	VIII	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) bezzii</i> (Corti, 1914)	6, 15, 28, 29, 31, 44, 86, 111, 112	◆◆	1200-2200	ena, ? hom	IV-V, XI	64, 116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) degrangei</i> Dorier et Grenier, 1959	2, 6, 15, 31, 69, 86, 112	◆◆	700-2200	cse	VI	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) ibariense</i> Zivkovich & Grenier, 1959	82	◆◆	868	csee	VI	116

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo- graphical	
<i>Simulium (Simulium) maximum</i> Knoz, 1961	2, 15, 28, 50, 63, 77, 86, 112, 144	◆◆	450-2200	e, cse	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) monticola</i> Friederichs, 1920	2, 15, 69, 86, 105, 112, 117, 123, 144, 155	◆◆	600-2200	ena	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) morsitans</i> Edwards, 1915	41, 86, 112, 133	◆◆	1400-2000	des	117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) noelleri</i> Friederichs, 1920	3, 6, 86, 112, 155	◆◆	800-1800	wces	117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) colombaschense</i> (Scopoli, 1780)	62.	●	1800-2250	cse	64
<i>Simulium (Simulium) ornatum</i> (Meigen, 1818)	79		780-960	tp, ? e	116
<i>Simulium (Simulium) reptans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	2, 6, 15, 28, 31, 41, 81, 86, 100, 105, 112, 155	◆◆	800-2000	hoes, h	64, 116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) tuberosum</i> (Lundstrom, 1911)	3, 15, 28, 31, 41, 62, 86, 105, 133, 155	◆◆	500-2300	h	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) variegatum</i> Meigen, 1818	2, 3, 6, 15, 28, 31, 41, 63, 69, 76, 79, 86, 112, 133, 155	◆◆	400-2300	e, ? cse	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Simulium) verecundum</i> Stone & Jamnback, 1955	6, 15, 28, 31, 86, 112	◆◆	1000-2000	h	117
<i>Simulium (Hellichella) latipes</i> Meigen, 1804	2, 15, 28, 31, 63, 69, 77, 105, 144	◆◆	900-2200	tp, ? h	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) angustipes</i> Edwards, 1915	3, 6, 28, 31, 41, 86, 112, 155	◆◆	900-2240	wp	117
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) aureum</i> Fries, 1824	3, 86, 112, 160	◆◆	700-2000	wes, ? h	116, 117
<i>Simulium (Eusimulium) velutinum</i> (Santos Abreu, 1922)	3, 31, 86	●	1000-2000	ena	117
<i>Simulium (Obuchovia) auricoma</i> Meigen, 1818	2, 6, 15, 31, 63, 69, 86, 105, 112, 113, 155	◆◆	1000-2400	ena	116, 117
Ceratopogonidae / 6					
<i>Culicoides (Avaritia) obsoletus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	21		1230-1390	h	182
<i>Culicoides festivipennis</i> Kieffer, 1914	109			tp	182
<i>Culicoides (Silvaticulicoides) pallidicornis</i> Kieffer, 1919	21		1230-1390	tp	182
<i>Culicoides pictipennis</i> (Staeger, 1839)	84, 85	●	2400-2900	wcp	182
<i>Dasyhelea (Dasyhelea) flavifrons</i> (Guerin, 1833)	48	●	2200	tp, ? hoess	174
<i>Forcipomyia (Forcipomyia) pallidipes</i> Santos Abreu, 1918	21		1230-1390	mwca	182

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical		
Chironomidae / 53						
<i>Anatopynia plumipes</i> (Fries, 1823)	70, 71, 119, 120, 146	•	2283-2340	e	VII-IX	161, 162, 164, 165
<i>Guttipolopia guttipennis</i> (Wulp, 1861)	119, 120	•	2250-2324	h	VII-IX	162
<i>Larsia curticalcar</i> (Kieffer, 1918)	3, 36, 119, 120, 123, 146	•	800-2440	e	IV, VI, X	49, 153, 161, 164
<i>Trissopelopia flavida</i> Kieffer, 1923	10, 73, 75, 76		340-900	et	IV, VI-IX	51, 153
<i>Zavrelimyia melanura</i> (Meigen, 1804)	3	•	1070-1850	tp	V-VI	49
<i>Diamesa (Diamesa) insignipes</i> Kieffer, 1908	3, 97, 123	•	1500-2440	h	V-VII	49, 162,
<i>Pothastia gaedii</i> (Meigen, 1838)	3	•	1070-1850	ho	VIII	49
<i>Pseudodiamesa (Pseudodiamesa) nivosa</i> (Goetghebuer, 1928)	87		1040	wcp	XI	49
<i>Prodiamesa olivacea</i> (Meigen, 1818)	3, 87, 124	•	1040-2196	h	V, VII, XI	50
<i>Acricotopus lucens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1850)	103		1140-1950	h		140
<i>Brillia bifida</i> (Kieffer, 1909)	12, 120, 125, 134	•	1040-2535	po	III, VII-XI	49, 162
<i>Corynoneura celeripes</i> Winnertz, 1852	159	•	2178	h	VIII	50
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) algarum</i> (Kieffer, 1911)	10, 36, 59, 70, 71, 99, 120, 121, 146	•	400-2394	e, ? wes	V-VI, VIII	49, 161, 162, 163, 164, 165, 166
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) annulator</i> Goetghebuer, 1927	16, 17, 18, 19	•	480-2030	h	VI-VII	166
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) fuscus</i> (Kieffer, 1909)	73		340	h	VII, XI	153
<i>Cricotopus (Cricotopus) tremulus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	120	•	2250	h		161
<i>Cricotopus (Isocladius) sylvestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	16, 17, 19, 32, 75, 97, 119, 120, 123, 125, 146	•	370-2535	hno	V-VIII,	49, 51, 161, 162, 163, 164, 166
<i>Eukiefferiella brevicar</i> (Kieffer, 1911)	18	•	1568	wp		166
<i>Eukiefferiella clypeata</i> (Thienemann, 1919)	98	•	1550	wp		166
<i>Eukiefferiella gracci</i> (Edwards, 1929)	46		1170-1200	h	V-VIII, XI	49
<i>Eukiefferiella similis</i> Goetghebuer, 1939	3, 16, 31, 36	•	900-2350	tp	VI-VII, XI	49, 51, 166
<i>Linnophyes minimus</i> (Meigen, 1818)	76		860-900	hptn	II, VII	153
? <i>Orthocladius murvanidzei</i> (Chernovskij, 1949)	119, 120, 123	•	2250-2440	wces	VI-VII	161
? <i>Paracladius inaequalis</i> Kieffer, 1926	36, 46		800-1200	? e	VI-XI	49, 51
<i>Psectrocladius (Psectrocladius) psilopterus</i> (Kieffer, 1906)	119, 120	•	2250-2324	h	VII	162

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Psectrocladius (Psectrocladius) simulans</i> (Johannsen, 1937)	119, 120, 121	•	2228-2324	h	162
<i>Rheocricotopus (Rheocricotopus) effusus</i> (Walker, 1856)	104		850-1150	ho	140
<i>Synorthocladus semivirens</i> (Kieffer, 1909)	31, 36, 46, 59, 65, 88, 120	•	980-2250	h	49, 50, 153, 161, 166
<i>Thienemannia gracilis</i> Kieffer, 1909	3	•	1070-1850	e	49
<i>Thienemanniella acuticornis</i> (Kieffer, 1912)	74		512	wp	51, 153
<i>Thienemanniella flaviforceps</i> Kieffer, 1925	3, 10	•	350-1850	e	49, 153
<i>Tvetenia bavarica</i> (Goetghebuer, 1934)	16		480	h	166
<i>Tvetenia calvescens</i> (Edwards, 1929)	3, 10, 12, 17, 18, 31, 36, 46, 53, 65, 98, 120	•	400-2250	wp	49, 50, 51, 153, 161, 166
<i>Zalutschia mucronata</i> (Brundin, 1949)	10, 36, 59		350-1000	wes	153
<i>Chironomus (Lobochironomus) dorsalis</i> Meigen, 1818	27, 125	•	2353-2535	h	162
<i>Chironomus (Chironomus) plumosus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	119, 120	•	2250-2324	hno	161
<i>Chironomus (Chironomus) riparius</i> Meigen, 1804	10, 15, 14, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 26, 27, 70, 71, 97, 119, 120, 122, 123, 124, 125, 134, 146, 149, 151, 152	•♦	400-2535	hn	51, 161, 162, 163, 2002, 165, 166
<i>Cryptochironomus (Cryptochironomus) defectus</i> (Kieffer, 1913)	18, 19, 20, 27, 70, 71, 89, 90, 92, 94, 119, 120, 123, 125, 134, 146, 147, 148, 150, 151, 152	•♦	2020-2545	pa	161, 162, 163, 164, 165, 166, 167
<i>Orthocladus (Eudactylocladius) fuscimanus</i> (Kieffer, 1908)	36		800-1000	wp	51
<i>Demicryptochironomus (Demicryptochironomus) vulheratus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	18, 121	•	1568-2228	po	162, 166
<i>Dicrotendipes nervosus</i> (Staeger, 1839)	18, 71, 119, 123, 124, 146, 149, 151	•	1568-2440	ho	161, 162, 164, 165, 166
<i>Einfieldia longipes</i> (Staeger, 1839)	27, 119, 123	•	2324-2440	h	162
<i>Endochironomus dispar</i> (Meigen, 1830)	36		800-1000	hoes	51
<i>Glyptotendipes (Glyptotendipes) pallens</i> (Meigen, 1804)	18, 98	•	1550-1568	po	166
<i>Paratendipes nudisquama</i> (Edwards, 1929)	3, 11, 107		440-1140	hno	49, 51
<i>Polypedium (Pentapedium) exsectum</i> (Kieffer, 1916)	7	•	2200	des	50
<i>Polypedium (Pentapedium) sordens</i> (van der Wulp, 1875)	120	•	2250	h	161

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical		
<i>Polypedium (Polypedium) nubeculosum</i> (Meigen, 1804)	70, 119, 120, 121, 123, 125	●	2228-2535	h	V-X	162, 165
<i>Polypedium (Tripodura) scalaenum</i> (Schrank, 1803)	3, 11, 19, 31, 36, 46	●	440-2003	ho	V-VIII	49, 51, 166
<i>Cladotanytarsus (Cladotanytarsus) manicus</i> (Walker, 1856)	10, 11, 36		400-1000	h	VI-XI	51, 153
<i>Microsectra junci</i> (Meigen, 1818)	10, 36, 70, 121, 122, 124	●	400-2368	h	VI-VII, X	51, 153, 162, 165
<i>Microsectra radialis</i> Goetghebuer 1939	90, 93	●	2545-2709	po		167
<i>Tanytarsus gregarius</i> Kieffer, 1909	3, 10, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 36, 46, 64, 65, 75, 88, 89, 91, 93, 94, 95, 97, 99, 119, 120, 123	◆◆	400-2709	h	VI-XI	49, 51, 153, 166, 167
BRACHYCERA ORTHORRHAPHA						
STRATIOMYOMORPHA						
Coenomyiidae / 1						
<i>Coenomyia ferruginea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	111	◆	1147	h		102
Stratiomyidae / 5						
<i>Chloromyia formosa</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	36, 111	◆	800-1147	h	V-VIII	3, 102
<i>Stratiomyia singularior</i> (Harris, 1776)	39		550	tp	V-VII	102
<i>Lasiopa baltus</i> (Walker, 1849)	109		300-1000	ban	V-VIII	169
<i>Lasiopa calva</i> (Meigen, 1822)	109, 111	◆	1147	cse	V-VIII	3, 144
<i>Pachygaster atra</i> (Panzer, 1798)	109		1700	eswa	VI-VIII	3
TABANOMORPHA						
Rhagionidae / 5						
<i>Chrysopilus cristatus</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	109	●	1200	e	VI-VIII	145
<i>Chrysopilus maerens</i> Loew, 1873	85, 111	◆◆	1147-2600	cseel	VII-VIII	169
<i>Rhagio conspicuus</i> Meigen, 1804	109	●	550-1800	e	V-VII	144, 145, 155, 169
<i>Rhagio scolopaceus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111	◆◆	1150	wes	V-VI	102
<i>Rhagio tringarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	39		550	wes	IV-VIII	102, 145
Tabanidae / 25						
<i>Nemoria vitripennis</i> (Meigen, 1820)	109			cseit	VI-VII	145
<i>Chrysops (Chrysops) caecutiens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	14, 36		400-900	hoes, ? tp	VI-IX	52, 57

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo- graphical	
<i>Alyotus fulvus</i> (Meigen, 1804)	9, 21, 59, 109	●	900-2550	tp	54, 145
<i>Hybomitra aterrima</i> (Meigen, 1820)	9, 21, 42, 57, 59, 131	●	900-2654	cse, m	54, 145
<i>Hybomitra auripila</i> (Meigen, 1820)	9, 21, 59, 109	●	900-2550	e	54, 145
<i>Hybomitra ciureai</i> (Séguy, 1937)	46, 66	●	1200-1800	esca	66, 68
<i>Hybomitra distinguenda</i> (Verrall, 1909)	66	●	1800	hoes, ? tp	66, 68
<i>Hybomitra micans</i> (Meigen, 1804)	23, 46, 66, 111	◆	1150-2100	e	66, 68, 102
<i>Hybomitra montana</i> (Meigen, 1820)	21, 59, 109	●	900-1390	hoes, ? tp	54
<i>Hybomitra tropica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21, 59, 109,	●	900-1390	e	54
<i>Tabanus bovinus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	46, 66, 109	●	1200-1800	tp, ? hop	68, 102
<i>Tabanus bromius</i> Linnaeus, 1758	39, 46, 66	●	550-1800	wp	54, 66, 141
<i>Tabanus cordiger</i> Meigen, 1820	46, 66	●	1200-1800	wp	68
<i>Tabanus glaucopsis</i> Meigen, 1820	22, 39, 66	●	550-1800	esca	54, 66
<i>Tabanus maculicornis</i> Zetterstedt, 1842	46	●	1200-1600	wes	66
<i>Tabanus miki</i> Brauer, 1880	21, 46, 59	●	900-1600	eit	54, 66, 68
<i>Tabanus quatuorotatus</i> Meigen, 1820	109	●	1200	wp	132, 141
<i>Tabanus spodopterus</i> Meigen, 1820	9, 21, 109	●	1200-2550	? csean	54, 132, 141, 145, 147
<i>Tabanus tergestinus</i> Egger, 1859	22, 46, 109	●	1200-1600	eit	54, 66, 145
<i>Tabanus unifasciatus</i> Loew, 1858	46	●	1200-1600	? wp	68
<i>Haematopota grandis</i> Meigen, 1820	21, 109	●	1200-1400	wp	54
<i>Haematopota italica</i> Meigen, 1804	109	●		eanna	145
<i>Haematopota pluvialis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	46, 109	●	1600	wcp	66, 102, 145
<i>Philpomyia aprica</i> (Meigen, 1820)	21, 59, 109	●	900-1400	eit, ? cseit	47, 54, 141
<i>Philpomyia graeca</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	8, 22, 59	●	900-2000	csea	54
Bombyliidae / 9					
<i>Bombyliella atra</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	23, 39, 111	◆	550-2100	tp	102
<i>Bombylius (Bombylius) major</i> Linnaeus, 1758	39, 110, 111, 140	◆	545-1900	ho	102
<i>Bombylius (Bombylius) medius</i> Linnaeus, 1758	23, 39, 110, 111, 140	◆	545-2100	wcp	102
<i>Bombylius (Bombylius) minor</i> Linnaeus, 1758	111	◆	1147	esca	102

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Lomatia sabei</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	39		550	? mwca	102
<i>Exoprosopa capucina</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	109			hoes, ? tp	145
<i>Hemipenthes maura</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	109			esca	245
<i>Hemipenthes morio</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	109			h	145
<i>Villa hottentotta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	39		550	tp	102
Therevidae / 2					
<i>Pandivirilia eximia</i> (Meigen, 1820)	21, 109		1200-1400	e	144, 145
<i>Thereva tuberculata</i> Loew, 1847	21		1200-1400	sena	145
Asilidae / 23					
<i>Chorades fimbriata</i> (Meigen, 1820)	111	◆	1200	wes	169
<i>Chorades ignea</i> (Meigen, 1820)	59		900	wes	145
<i>Laphria flava</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	22, 59, 85, 111	◆◆	900-2500	po	144, 145, 169
<i>Laphria gibbosa</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	21		1200-1400	hoes	169
<i>Dioctria cothurnata</i> Meigen, 1820	109			wces	144, 145
<i>Dioctria oelandica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	39, 111	◆	550-1200	e	102, 145
<i>Lasitopogon cinctus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	9, 24, 85	●	1789-2600	e	144, 145
<i>Lasitopogon montanus</i> Schiner, 1862	158		1374	? cse	101
<i>Cyrtopogon ruficornis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	158		1374	e	101
<i>Dasyopogon diadema</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	109			wp	144
<i>Leptogaster cylindrica</i> (De Geer, 1776)	39		550	tp	102
<i>Dysmachus cephalenus</i> Loew, 1871	158		1374	ban	101
<i>Dysmachus fuscipennis</i> (Meigen, 1820)	109		1500	? wes	85
<i>Dysmachus stylifer</i> (Loew, 1854)	109, 158		1374	cse	101, 144, 145
<i>Didymachus picipes</i> (Meigen, 1820)	23, 39, 111, 140	◆◆	550-2100	wes	102
<i>Erax barbatus</i> Scopoli, 1763	10		350-400	e	144, 145
<i>Eutolmus rufibarbis</i> (Meigen, 1820)	109			tp	144, 145
<i>Neotamius cothurnatus</i> (Meigen, 1820)	109			e	144, 145
<i>Neotamius cyanurus</i> (Loew, 1849)	111, 158	◆	1200-1450	hoes	101, 102

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo- graphical	
<i>Neomochtherus geniculatus</i> (Meigen, 1820)	109			e, ? cse	VII-VIII 144, 145
<i>Stilpnogaster aemula</i> (Meigen, 1820)	21, 107		850-1300	e	VII-VIII 145
<i>Tolmerus atricapillus</i> (Fallen, 1814)	21, 114	◆	1200-1400	hoes, ? tp	VII-VIII 144, 145
<i>Tolmerus bolgarcus</i> Lehr, 1981	116		1000-1100	Ebg	133
Empididae / 8					
<i>Empis (Euempis) ciliata</i> Fabricius, 1787	111	◆	1200	des	V 102
<i>Empis (Euempis) tessellata</i> Fabricius, 1794	23, 39, 110, 111, 140	◆◆	545-2100	hop	V-VII 102
<i>Empis (Polyblepharis) opaca</i> Meigen, 1804	109			e	VI 145
<i>Rhamphomyia (Rhamphomyia) sulcata</i> (Meigen, 1804)	109			hoes	IV-VII 144
<i>Rhamphomyia (Rhamphomyia) tibialis</i> Meigen, 1822	111	◆	1200	des	102
<i>Rhamphomyia (Holodera) culicina</i> (Fallen, 1816)	109			e	V 5, 6
<i>Chelifera precabunda</i> Collin, 1961	109			? e	V 103
<i>Wiedemannia (Chamaedipsa) lota</i> Walker, 1851	109			eswa	VI 103
Hybotidae / 5					
<i>Bicellaria nigra</i> (Meigen, 1824)	156		930-1000	e	V-VI 63
<i>Platypalpus maculipes</i> (Meigen, 1829)	156		930-1000	e	V 33
<i>Platypalpus niger</i> (Meigen, 1804)	156		930-1000	e	V, VIII 63
<i>Platypalpus pallidicornis</i> (Collin, 1926)	156		930-1000	e	V-VI 63
<i>Drapetis (Drapetis) assimilis</i> (Fallen, 1815)	156		930-1000	e, ? h	V 63
Dolichopodidae / 25					
<i>Rhaphium crassipes</i> (Meigen, 1824)	158		1374-1400	wes	VII 111
<i>Rhaphium monotrichum</i> Loew, 1850	158		1374-1400	wces	VI 112, 113
<i>Hydrophorus balticus</i> (Meigen, 1824)	158		1374-1400	ppt	VI-VIII 112
<i>Sympycnus desoutteri</i> Parent, 1925	158		1374-1400	e	V-IX 110, 112
<i>Syntormon denticulatum</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	158		1374-1400	wes	VII 111
<i>Syntormon fuscipes</i> (von Roser, 1840)	158		1374-1400	e	V 110
<i>Syntormon monile</i> (Haliday, 1815)	158		1374-1400	wp	VI, X 110, 111
<i>Syntormon pallipes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	158		1374-1400	wp	IV-IX 110, 111

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Syntormon pumilum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	158		1374-1400	wp	V-X 111
<i>Campsicnemus curvipes</i> (Fallén, 1823)	158		1374-1400	ena	V-IX 112
<i>Argyra auricollis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	158		1374-1400	e	VII 112
<i>Chrysotus gramineus</i> (Fallén, 1823)	97, 158	•	1374-1530	tp	VII 110, 112
<i>Chrysotus laevis</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)	158		1374-1400	hoes	VI-VII 112
<i>Chrysotus pulchellus</i> Kowarz, 1874	158		1374-1400	po	V-VI 112
<i>Gymnopternus angustifrons</i> (Staeger, 1842)	158		1374-1400	wes	VI-VII 112
<i>Gymnopternus brevicornis</i> (Staeger 1842)	158		1374-1400	e	VI-VIII 112
<i>Hercostomus sahlbergi</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	52		1000-1750	e	145
<i>Dolichopus lepidus</i> Staeger, 1842	158		1374-1400	po	VI-VII 112
<i>Dolichopus pennatus</i> Meigen, 1824	158		1374-1400	po	VI-VII 110, 111, 112
<i>Dolichopus phaeopus</i> Haliday, 1851	8	•	2000	e	VII-IX 29
<i>Dolichopus pictipes</i> Meigen, 1824	158		1374-1400	wes	VI 112, 113
<i>Dolichopus plumipes</i> (Scopoli, 1783)	158		1374-1400	hno	VI 111, 112
<i>Dolichopus popularis</i> Wiedemann, 1817	158		1374-1400	wces	VI-VII 112
<i>Dolichopus simplex</i> Meigen, 1824	158		1374-1400	wes	V-VII 110, 111, 112
<i>Dolichopus unguilatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	158		1374-1400	h	VI-VII 110, 111, 112
BRACHYCERA CYCLORRHAPHA					
ASCHIZA					
Platypzeidae / 1					
<i>Callomyia saibhira</i> Chandler, 1976	156		930-1000	des	25, 46
Phoridae / 1					
<i>Triphleba bicornuta</i> (Strobl, 1910)	84	•	2000-2100	e	VIII-X 32
Syrphidae / 149					
<i>Dasyrphus albostrigatus</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21		1200-1400	tp	V-VI 56
<i>Dasyrphus venustus</i> (Meigen, 1822)	22, 46, 66	•	1200-2000	h	V-IX 4, 56
<i>Didea alneti</i> (Fallen, 1817)	85	•	2925	h	56
<i>Doros profuges</i> (Harris 1780)	21		1200-1400	hoes	56

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Epistrophe diaphana</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	21		1200-1400	esca	56
<i>Epistrophe elegans</i> (Harris, 1780)	21		1200-1400	et	56
<i>Epistrophe grossulariae</i> (Meigen, 1822)	109			h	VI-VII, IX
<i>Epistrophe nitidicollis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21		1200-1400	h	IV-X
<i>Epistrophella euchroma</i> (Kowarz, 1885)	97	●	1500-1550	hoes	56
<i>Episyrrhus balteatus</i> (De Geer, 1776)	111	◆	1147	poa	IV-X
<i>Leucozona lucorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	97, 137, 145	●	1500-2300	h	56
<i>Melangyna lasiophthalma</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	69	●	1800	esca	VI
<i>Meligrama guttata</i> (Fallen, 1817)	21		1200-1400	h	56
<i>Meligrama triangulifera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	21		1200-1400	h	IX-X
<i>Meliscaeva auricollis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21		1200-1400	wp	IV-VIII
<i>Meliscaeva cinctella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	46		1170-1200	ho	VI
<i>Eupeodes lapponicus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	21		1200-1400	h	V-VI
<i>Eupeodes corollae</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21, 59, 97	●	900-1550	ppta	III-X
<i>Eupeodes latifasciatus</i> (Macquart, 1829)	111	◆	1147	ho	IV-VIII
<i>Eupeodes luniger</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21		1200-1400	ho	V-X
<i>Parasyrphus lineolus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	66	●	1800	h	VI
<i>Parasyrphus malinellus</i> (Collin, 1952)	66	●	1800	des	V-VI
<i>Parasyrphus lineolus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	21		1200-1400	h	VIII-IX
<i>Eupeodes nitens</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	10, 158		400-1374	tp	VIII-IX
<i>Scaeva pyrastris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	ho	VI-X
<i>Sphaerophoria menthastris</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	hop	VI-X
<i>Sphaerophoria philantha</i> (Meigen, 1822)	39		550-650	h	V-X
<i>Sphaerophoria scripta</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	36, 39, 46, 55, 110, 111, 140	◆	550-1900	ho	V-X
<i>Syrphus ribesii</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	36, 116		800-1100	h	IV-X
<i>Syrphus vitripennis</i> Meigen, 1822	36, 109		800-1000	ho	IV-X
<i>Xanthogramma pedissequum</i> (Harris, 1776)	97	●	1500-1550	tp	IV-VIII
<i>Baccha elongata</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	111	◆	1147	h	V-X

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Chrysotoxum arcuatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	10, 21, 59, 97, 111	◆◆	400-1550	tp	VII-VIII 56; 138
<i>Chrysotoxum elegans</i> Loew, 1841	21, 97	●	1200-1550	e	V-IX 56
<i>Chrysotoxum fasciolatum</i> (De Geer, 1776)	21, 97	●	1200-1550	h	VI 56
<i>Chrysotoxum festivum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	58, 111	◆	450-1147	po	V-VIII 4, 102
<i>Chrysotoxum intermedium</i> (Meigen, 1822)	97	●	1500-1550	wp	VI 56
<i>Chrysotoxum octomaculatum</i> Curtis, 1837	21	●	1200-1400	wes	V 56
<i>Chrysotoxum vernale</i> Loew, 1841	10		350-450	esca	V-VII 138
<i>Melanostoma mellinum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	23, 36, 39, 46, 110, 111, 140	◆◆	540-2100	h	IV-X 4, 102, 137
<i>Xanthandrus comtus</i> (Harris, 1780)	21, 97	●	1200-1550	po	VI, X 56
<i>Platycheirus ambiguus</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21		1200-1400	ho	V 56
<i>Platycheirus albimanus</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	66	●	1800	ho	VI-VIII 4
<i>Platycheirus clypeatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)	111	◆	1147	h	VI-VIII 102
<i>Platycheirus fulviventris</i> (Macquart, 1829)	21		1200-1400	esca	VI-VIII 56
<i>Platycheirus manicatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21, 59		900-1400	h	56
<i>Platycheirus melanopsis</i> Loew, 1856	66	●	1800	des	VI 4
<i>Platycheirus peltatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)	55, 97, 111	◆◆	1147-1550	h	56, 102
<i>Platycheirus podagratus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	59		900	h	VI-VIII 56
<i>Platycheirus scutatus</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21, 46		1170-1400	h	V-VII 4, 56
<i>Paragus albifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)	111	◆	1147	tp	VI-VIII 169
<i>Paragus bicolor</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	10, 59, 110, 111, 158	◆	400-1374	h	V-X 56, 138, 145, 169
<i>Paragus cinctus</i> Schiner & Egger, 1853	109			? mt	V-VIII 145
<i>Paragus haemorrhous</i> Meigen, 1822	21		1200-1400	hat	VI-VIII 56
<i>Paragus quadrfasciatus</i> Meigen, 1822	97	●	1500-1550	tp	V-X 56
<i>Paragus tibialis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	10, 21, 36		400-1400	ho	V-X 4, 56, 138
<i>Pipiza austriaca</i> Meigen, 1822	158		1374-1400	hoes	56, 138
<i>Pipiza quadrimaculata</i> (Panzer, 1804)	109			h	4
<i>Pipizella virens</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	46, 59		900-1200	tp	V-VIII 4, 56
<i>Trichopsomyia flavitarsis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	59		900	hoes	56

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References		
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)		Areo- graphical	Fenology
<i>Triglyphus primus</i> Loew, 1840	97	●	1500-1550	hoes, ? tp	V-VI	56
<i>Chamaesyrrhus scaevoides</i> (Fallén, 1817)	46		1200	des	V-VI	4
<i>Cheiliosia albitarsis</i> (Meigen, 1822)	46, 55, 66	◆◆	1200-1800	h	V-VI	4, 102
<i>Cheiliosia barbata</i> Loew, 1857	59		900	e	IV-VII	56
<i>Cheiliosia canicularis</i> (Panzer, 1801)	21, 36		900-1400	hoes	VII-VIII	52, 53, 57
<i>Cheiliosia illustrata</i> (Harris, 1780)	21, 97	●	1200-1550	hoes	V-VI	56
<i>Cheiliosia impressa</i> Loew, 1840	21, 66	●	1200-1800	hoes	VI	4, 56
<i>Cheiliosia latifrons</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	21		1200-1400	wp		56
<i>Cheiliosia melanopa</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	14, 59, 97	●	400-1550	e	V-VII	56
<i>Cheiliosia melanura</i> (Becker, 1894)	66	●	1800	des	V-VI	4
<i>Cheiliosia morio</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	14, 97	●	400-1550	wces	V	56
<i>Cheiliosia mutabilis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21		1200-1400	wcp	IV-VI	56
<i>Cheiliosia pagana</i> (Meigen, 1822)	97	●	1500-1550	h	VI	56
<i>Cheiliosia pallipes</i> Loew, 1863	97	●	1500-1550	h		56
<i>Cheiliosia proxima</i> (Zetterstedt, 1843)	21, 111	◆	1150-1400	hoes	V-VIII	56, 102
<i>Cheiliosia pubera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	66	●	1800	e	VI	4
<i>Cheiliosia rhynchops</i> Egger, 1860	66	●	1800	e	VI	4
<i>Cheiliosia ruralis</i> (Meigen, 1822) [<i>Ch. urbana</i> (Meigen, 1822)]	111	◆	1150	hoes, ? tp	IV-VI	102
<i>Cheiliosia schineri</i> Egger, 1860	97	●	1500-1550	se		56
<i>Cheiliosia semifasciata</i> (Becker, 1894)	54	◆		e	V	44
<i>Cheiliosia variabilis</i> (Panzer, 1798)	55	◆	1350-1475	wcp	VI-VIII	102
<i>Cheiliosia velutina</i> Loew, 1840	10, 36		400-1000	hoes	V-VIII	4, 138
<i>Cheiliosia vernalis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21		1200-1400	hoes	V	4
<i>Cheiliosia vulpina</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21		1200-1400	e	VI-VIII	145
<i>Ferdinandea cuprea</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	21		1200-1400	tp	V-VII	56
<i>Peleccera trincta</i> Meigen, 1822	21		1200-1400	des	VIII	169
<i>Rhingia campestris</i> Meigen, 1822	55	◆	1350-1475	hoes	VII	102
<i>Rhingia rostrata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	wes	V	56

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Volucella bombylans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111, 85		1150-2500	h	102, 145, 169
<i>Volucella inanis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21, 111, 137	◆◆	1150-2000	esca	56, 169
<i>Volucella pellucens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	109			po	102
<i>Volucella zonaria</i> (Poda, 1761)	21, 111	◆	1150-1400	tp	4, 102, 145
<i>Brachyopa bicolor</i> (Fallén, 1817)	97	●	1500-1550	? hoes	56
<i>Brachyopa panzeri</i> Goffe, 1945	111	◆	1147	des	102
<i>Melanogaster parumplicata</i> (Loew, 1840)	21		1200-1400	? hoes	56
<i>Chrysogaster solstitialis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21, 109		900-1400	ena	53, 57
<i>Pipizella viduata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	36, 39, 66, 111	◆◆	550-1800	e	4, 102, 137
<i>Lejogaster metallina</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	21		1200-1400	tp	56
<i>Lejogaster tarsata</i> (Meigen, 1822)	59, 97	●	900-1550	esca, ? tp	56
<i>Orthonevra elegans</i> (Meigen, 1822)	21		1200-1400	hoes	56
<i>Orthonevra geniculata</i> (Meigen 1830)	97	●	1500-1550	hoes	56
<i>Orthonevra nobilis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21, 46		1170-1400	esca	4, 56
<i>Neoascia amexa</i> (Müller, 1776)	109			e	102
<i>Neoascia podagrica</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	39		550-650	wcp	137
<i>Neoascia meticulosa</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	66	●	1800	hoes ? esca	4
<i>Neoascia geniculata</i> (Meigen, 1822)	66	●	1800	wces	4
<i>Sphagina clunipes</i> (Fallen, 1816)	21, 66	●	1200-1800	des	4, 56, 145
<i>Sphagina montana</i> Becker, 1921	21		1200-1400	e	56
<i>Arctophila bequaerti</i> Herve-Bazin, 1913	12, 36		900-1000	ban	52
<i>Arctophila bombiforme</i> (Fallén, 1810)	21, 57, 97, 111, 158	◆◆	1150-2145	e	56, 102, 138, 145
<i>Sericomyia lappona</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	66	●	1800	hoes	4
<i>Sericomyia silentis</i> (Harris, 1776)	21, 111	◆	1150-1400	hoes	56, 169
<i>Eumerus strigatus</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21, 36, 46		800-1500	ha, ? i	4, 56
<i>Merodon aberrans</i> Egger, 1860	111	◆	1150	ena	169
<i>Merodon aeneus</i> Meigen, 1822	21, 111	◆	1150-1400	ena	145, 169
<i>Merodon avidus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	21, 111	◆	1150-1400	ena	102, 169

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Merodon cinereus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	109			145
<i>Merodon clavipes</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	97	●	1500-1550	145
<i>Merodon equestris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	109		ha	102
<i>Merodon loewi</i> van der Goot, 1964	97	●	1500-1550	56
<i>Merodon ruficornis</i> Meigen, 1822	36, 66	●	800-1800	4
<i>Merodon rufus</i> Meigen, 1838	109		ena	145
<i>Merodon testaceus</i> Sack, 1913	97	●	1500-1550	56
<i>Psilota anthracina</i> Meigen, 1822	14, 97	●	400-1550	56
<i>Psarus abdominalis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	97	●	1500-1550	56
<i>Ceriana conopsoidea</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	56
<i>Eristalinus aeneus</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	10		350-400	138
<i>Eristalinus sepulchralis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111	◆	1150	102
<i>Eristalis arbustorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	36, 39, 66, 109, 111, 158	●	550-1800	102, 137, 138, 145, 169
<i>Eristalis horticola</i> (De Geer, 1776)	21, 66	●	1200-1800	4, 56
<i>Eristalis intricaria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	111	◆	1150	102
<i>Eristalis jugorum</i> Egger, 1858	66	●	1800	4
<i>Eristalis nemorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758) ?	10, 21, 59		350-1400	52, 56, 145
<i>Eristalis cryptarum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21		1200-1400	56
<i>Eristalis similis</i> (Fallén, 1817)	66, 111	◆	1150-1800	4, 169
<i>Eristalis rupium</i> Fabricius, 1805	21, 66	●	1200-1800	4, 169
<i>Eristalis tenax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	39, 109, 158		550-1374	102, 137, 138
<i>Helophilus hybridus</i> Loew, 1846	10, 158		350-1374	56; 238
<i>Helophilus trivittatus</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	39, 111	◆	550-1150	102
<i>Helophilus pendulus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	36		800-1000	4
<i>Blera fallax</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	56
<i>Spilomyia saltuum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21		1200-1400	56
<i>Syrretta pipiens</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	36, 39, 109		550-1000	137, 145
<i>Brachypalpus laphniformis</i> (Fallén, 1816)	21		1200-1400	56

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical		
<i>Chalcosyrphus femoratus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	8	•	2100-2300	hoes ? esca	VI	56
<i>Xylota ignava</i> (Panzer, 1798)	21		1200-1400	tp	V-VI, X	56
<i>Xylota segnis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21, 109		1200-1400	h	V-VIII	56, 145, 169
<i>Xylota sylvarium</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	hoes	VI-VIII	145
<i>Microdon devius</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	55	♦	1350-1475	wces	VI	102
Pipunculidae / 5						
<i>Pipunculus campestris</i> Latreille, 1805	36		800-1000	ho	VI	3
<i>Eudorylas jenkinsoni</i> Coe, 1966	67	•	2729	e		124
<i>Dorylomorpha (Dorylomyia) incognita</i> (Verrall, 1901)	156, 142	•	930-1700	e		124
<i>Tomosvaryella coquilletti</i> (Kertész, 1907)	129		360	ho		124
<i>Tomosvaryella geniculata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	55	♦	1350-1475	e	VI, VIII	124
SCHIZOPHORA						
ACALYPTRATA						
Conopidae / 20						
<i>Conops (Asiconops) elegans</i> Meigen, 1824	59		900	hom	VII	58
<i>Conops (Conops) quadrifasciatus</i> De Geer, 1776	21, 109		1200-1400	esanca	VI-VIII	145, 169
<i>Conops (Conops) scutellatus</i> Meigen 1804	97, 111	♦♦	1150-1550	e	VIII	58, 169
<i>Conops (Conops) silaceus</i> Wiedemann in Meigen, 1824	97	•	1500-1550	se	VI-VIII	58
<i>Conops (Conops) vesicularis</i> Linnaeus, 1761	111	♦	1150	tp		102
<i>Conops (Conops) vitellinus</i> Loew, 1847	14		400-450	nm	V, VII	58
<i>Physocephala chrysoorrhoea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21, 109		1200-1400	tp, ? hop	VII	58
<i>Physocephala nigra</i> (De Geer, 1776)	59		900	tp, ? hop	V	58
<i>Physocephala variegata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21, 109		1200-1400	sp	VII-VIII	58
<i>Zodion cinereum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21, 109, 111	♦	1150-1500	po	VI-VIII	58, 145, 169
<i>Zodion erythrum</i> Rondani, 1865	21, 109		1200-1400	sp, ? tp	VII	58
<i>Zodion notatum</i> (Meigen, 1804)	36, 46		800-1200	hop	V-VIII	3
<i>Myopa buccata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	55, 66, 111	♦♦	1150-1800	tp	V-VII	3, 58, 102
<i>Myopa dorsalis</i> Fabricius, 1794	21, 109		1200-1400	wpo	V-VII	58

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References	
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)		
<i>Myopa testacea</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	21, 36, 109	●	800-1700	IV-VIII	3, 58
<i>Melanosoma bicolor</i> (Meigen 1824)	21		1200	V-VII	58
<i>Myopotta pallipes</i> (Wiedemann in Meigen, 1824)	10		400		58
<i>Thecophora atra</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	111	◆	1150	V-VIII	169
<i>Thecophora pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21, 116		1000-1400		58
<i>Sicus ferrugineus</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	21, 109, 111	◆	1150-1700	VI-VIII	3, 58, 102
Tephritidae / 8					
<i>Acidia cognata</i> (Wiedemann, 1817)	111	◆	1150-1300		44
<i>Euleia heradei</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	54, 109	●	2200	VIII	44
<i>Terellia (Terellia) colon</i> (Meigen 1826)	21		1200	VII-VIII	59
<i>Oxyna flavipennis</i> (Loew, 1844)	21		1200-1400	VI-VII	59
<i>Tephritis bardanae</i> (Schränk, 1803)	111, 114	◆	1150-1300	VI-VII	102
<i>Tephritis vespertina</i> (Loew, 1844)	21		1200-1400	VII	59
<i>Trypeta artemisiae</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	111	◆	1150	VIII	44
<i>Stenomocera cornuta</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	111, 113	◆	1150-1300	VIII	44
Lauxaniidae / 1					
<i>Calliopum aeneum</i> (Fallén, 1820)	109		900	IV-X	53
Cremifaniidae / 1					
<i>Cremifania bulgarica</i> L. Papp, 2010	40	●	2250	IX	148
Chamaemyiidae / 1					
<i>Chamaemyia subjunctorum</i> Tanasijtschuk, 1970	47	●	2500	IV-VII	23
Sciomyzidae / 2					
<i>Pherbellia cinerella</i> (Fallén, 1820)	59		900	VII	152
<i>Tetanocera ferruginea</i> Fallén, 1820	111, 114	◆	1150-1300	VIII	102
Agromyzidae / 48					
<i>Agromyza alnibetulae</i> Hendel, 1931	111, 114	◆	1150-1300	VIII	44
<i>Agromyza nana</i> Meigen 1830	158		1374	VI-VII	2
<i>Agromyza pseudoreptans</i> Nowakowski, 1967	158		1374		2

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Agromyza reptans</i> Fallen, 1823	111	◆	1700	ho	44
<i>Agromyza rufipes</i> Meigen, 1830	111	◆	1700	wpo	44
<i>Ophiomyia heringi</i> Stary, 1930	111	◆	1150-1300	e	44
<i>Ophiomyia labiatarum</i> Hering, 1937	111	◆	1150-1300	h	44
<i>Ophiomyia maura</i> (Meigen, 1838)	111	◆	1150-1300	h	44
<i>Amauromyza (Amauromyza) lamii</i> (Kaltenbach, 1858)	111	◆	1700	e	44
<i>Amauromyza (Amauromyza) morionella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	111	◆	1300	ena	44
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) flavifrons</i> (Meigen, 1830)	111, 160	◆	580-1150	h	44
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) gyrans</i> (Fallen 1823)	111	◆	1150-1200	e	44
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) labiatarum</i> (Hendel, 1920)	111	◆	1150-1200	e	44
<i>Amauromyza (Cephalomyza) verbasci</i> (Bouché, 1847)	111	◆	1150-1200	e	44
<i>Cerodontha (Poemyza) pygmaea</i> (Meigen 1830)	158		1374	h	2
<i>Liriomyza amoena</i> (Meigen, 1830)	160		580	wpo	44
<i>Liriomyza artemisicola</i> de Meijere, 1924	111	◆	1150-1200	wpo	44
<i>Liriomyza bulhri</i> Hering, 1937	160		580-660	e	44
<i>Liriomyza congesta</i> (Becker, 1903)	111, 158, 160	◆	580-1374	po	2, 44
<i>Liriomyza demeijerei</i> Hering, 1930	111	◆	1150-1200	e	44
<i>Liriomyza eupatorii</i> (Kaltenbach, 1873)	111	◆	1150-1200	h	2
<i>Liriomyza pascuum</i> (Meigen, 1838)	158		1374	e	2
<i>Liriomyza puella</i> (Meigen, 1830)	111	◆	1150-1200	e	44
<i>Liriomyza sonchi</i> Hendel, 1931	111, 160	◆	580-1200	ho	44
<i>Liriomyza strigata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	111, 160	◆	580-1200	po	44
<i>Liriomyza taraxaci</i> Hering, 1927	111, 158	◆	1150-1374	h	2, 44
<i>Phytoliriomyza melampyga</i> (Loew, 1869)	111	◆	1150-1200	h	44
<i>Phytoliriomyza variegata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	111, 160	◆	580-1200	po	44
<i>Calycomyza artemisiae</i> (Kaltenbach, 1856)	111	◆	1150-1200	hno	44
<i>Aulagromyza similis</i> (Brischke, 1880)	111	◆	1150-1200	e	44
<i>Aulagromyza tridentata</i> (Loew, 1858)	111, 160	◆	580-1200	ewca, ? eca	44

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Phytomyza affinis</i> Fallén, 1823	160		580-660	VIII e, ? h 44
<i>Phytomyza alpina</i> Groschke, 1957	158		1374	VIII e, ? h 2
<i>Phytomyza artemisivora</i> Spencer, 1971	111	◆	1150-1200	VIII ewca 44
<i>Phytomyza chaerophylli</i> (Kaltenbach, 1856)	109, 158, 160		580-1374	VIII e 2, 44
<i>Phytomyza cirsii</i> Hendel, 1923	111	◆	1150-1200	VIII e 44
<i>Phytomyza erigerophila</i> Hering, 1927	160		580-660	VIII e 44
<i>Phytomyza eupatorii</i> Hendel, 1927	111	◆	1150-1200	VIII wpo 44
<i>Phytomyza notata</i> Meigen, 1830	158		1374	VIII e 2
<i>Phytomyza obscura</i> Hendel, 1920	158		1374	VIII e, ? ena 2
<i>Phytomyza pastinacae</i> Hendel, 1923	111	◆	1150-1200	VIII h 44
<i>Phytomyza petoei</i> Hering, 1924	111, 158	◆	1150-1374	VIII wpo 2, 44
<i>Phytomyza ranunculivora</i> Hering, 1932	158		1374	VIII e 2
<i>Phytomyza salviae</i> (Hering, 1924)	111, 158	◆	1150-1374	VIII e 2, 44
<i>Phytomyza senecionis</i> Kaltenbach, 1869	111	◆	1150-1200	VIII e 44
<i>Phytomyza spondylii</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851	111	◆	1150-1200	VIII ho 44
<i>Phytomyza tetrasticha</i> Hendel, 1927	158, 160		580-1374	VIII e 2, 44
<i>Phytomyza tussilaginis</i> Hendel, 1925	158		1374	VIII h 2
Opomyzidae / 2				
<i>Opomyza florum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21, 84	●	1200-2389	V-XI e 33
<i>Geomyza tripunctata</i> Fallén, 1823	84	●	2389	V-X h 33
Milichiidae / 1				
<i>Madiza glabra</i> Fallén, 1820	8, 97	●	1400-2100	IV-X h 24
Chloropidae / 61				
<i>Aphanotrigonum trilineatum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	104		800-1150	IV-IX wces 27, 30
<i>Conioscinella frontella</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97	●	1500-1550	VI-VIII hoes 30
<i>Conioscinella sordidella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	97	●	1400	V-IX e 30
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) nigropilosus</i> Becker, 1910	104		800-1150	V-VII eit 30
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) raptus</i> (Haliday, 1838)	104		800-1150	IV-VII e 30

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Dicraeus (Dicraeus) tibialis</i> (Macquart, 1835)	104		800-1150	ha	V-VII 30
<i>Elachiptera cornuta</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97, 104, 158	●	800-1400	hop	IV-VII 30
<i>Elachiptera diastema</i> Collin, 1946	84	●	2000-2100	ena	V-X 30
<i>Gaurax fascipes</i> Becker, 1910	97	●	1400	e	IX 27, 30
<i>Hapleginella laevicollis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1858)	97	●	1400	hoes	IX 27, 30
<i>Incertella albipalpis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	97, 104, 158	●	800-1500	hoes	IV-X 39
<i>Incertella kerteszi</i> (Becker, 1910)	97	●	1400	hoes	VI-VIII 27
<i>Lasiambia palposa</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97	●	1400	? ho	VII-IX 27
<i>Lipara lucens</i> Meigen, 1830	14, 39		400-650	h*, ? wp	III-V 30
<i>Lipara pullitarsis</i> Doskocil & Chvala, 1971	83		460	e	III-V 27
<i>Lipara similis</i> Schiner, 1854	83		460	? wp	III-VI 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) alopecuri</i> Balachovsky & Mesnil, 1935	104		800-1150	e	V-IX 27
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) cariciphila</i> Collin, 1946	129		360	wces	V-VIII 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) frit</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	97, 104	●	800-1400	hpta, k	IV-X 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) maura</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97	●	1400	wes	V-X 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) nigerrima</i> (Macquart, 1835)	22, 84, 97, 103, 129	●	360-2100	e	IV-X 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) nitidissima</i> (Meigen, 1838)	14, 97	●	400-1400	h	IV-IX 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1830)	104		800-1150	hop	IV-X 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) vastator</i> (Curtis, 1845)	21, 104		800-1300	e	IV-X 30
<i>Oscinella (Oscinella) ventricosi</i> Nartshuk, 1955	14		400-450	wes	IV-X 30
<i>Oscinimorpha minutissima</i> (Strobl, 1900)	21, 97, 104	●	850-1400	wp	V-VIII 30, 169
<i>Oscinimorpha sordidissima</i> (Strobl, 1903)	97, 104	●	850-1400	e	V-VIII 30
<i>Polyodaspis ruficornis</i> (Macquart, 1835)	14		400-450	po	V-X 30
<i>Siphonella oscinima</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97	●	1400	h	VI-VIII 27
<i>Trachysiphonella ruficeps</i> (Macquart, 1835)	55, 97, 111	◆	1150-1600	e	V-X 30
<i>Tricimba (Nartshukiella) cincta</i> (Meigen, 1830)	104		800-1150	h	V-X 30
<i>Cetema (Cetema) cereris</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97, 104	●	850-1450	hoes	V-VIII 30
<i>Cetema (Cetema) elongatum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	55, 97, 104	●	850-1600	h	V-VIII 21, 22, 30

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Cetema (Cetema) myopinum</i> (Loew, 1866)	55, 64, 97	◆◆	1350-1800	VI-VIII wesca
<i>Cetema (Cetema) neglectum</i> Tonnoir, 1921	97	●	1450	VI-VIII e
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) calceatus</i> Meigen, 1830	97, 104	●	800-1400	V-X wces
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) geminatus</i> Meigen, 1830	97	●	1450	VI-VIII wces
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) hypostigma</i> Meigen, 1830	111	◆	1150-1200	V-X e
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) pumilionis</i> (Bjerkander, 1778)	21		1200-1400	V-X wp, ? wcp
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) speciosus</i> Meigen, 1830	97, 104, 158	●	850-1450	V-IX wes
<i>Chlorops (Chlorops) troglodytes</i> (Zetterstedt, 1848)	10, 97, 103, 158	●	400-1450	V-X wces
<i>Chlorops (Sclerophallus) limbatus</i> Meigen, 1830	14		360-400	V ? hoes
<i>Diplotoxa messoria</i> (Fallén, 1820)	97, 104	●	800-1400	VI-X h
<i>Elachiptericus italicus</i> Duda, 1933	129		360	V se
<i>Lasiosina herpini</i> (Guérin-Ménéville, 1843)	10, 158		400-1374	IV-IX tp
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) athletica</i> Fedoseeva, 1974	55, 97	◆◆	1450-1600	VI-IX csee
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) bohemica</i> Fedoseeva, 1962	55	◆	1600	VII-VIII e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) femorata</i> Macquart, 1835	97	●	1400-1450	VI-IX e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) mosquensis</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	45, 97	◆◆	900-1450	VI-VIII e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) nigriseta</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	104		850-1150	VI-VII wces
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) nigriventris</i> Macquart, 1835	55, 97, 111	◆◆	1150-1600	IV-X h
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) pratorum</i> Meigen, 1830	97	●	1400-1450	V-VIII h
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) rohndendorfi</i> Fedoseeva, 1974	104		850-1150	VII-VIII e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) rufa</i> Fedoseeva, 1962	45, 55, 97	◆◆	900-1600	VI-VIII e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) saltatrix</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	97, 104	●	850-1450	IV-X h
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) triangulina</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	104		850-1150	V-VII e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) variegata</i> Meigen 1830	111	◆	1150-1200	VII-IX e
<i>Meromyza (Meromyza) zahvatkini</i> Fedoseeva, 1960	55	◆	1600	VI-IX des
<i>Thaumatomyia glabra</i> (Meigen, 1830)	97, 129	●	360-1450	IV-X h
<i>Thaumatomyia hallandica</i> Andersson, 1966	97	●	1400-1450	V-VIII wces
<i>Thaumatomyia notata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	97, 104		850-1450	IV-X ppt

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				Fenology	References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical		
Heleomyzidae / 2						
<i>Orbellia borisregis</i> Czerny, 1930	117	•	2005	Er	II	48
<i>Scotiocentra (Leriola) nigrinervis</i> (Wahlgrén, 1918)	117	•	2000	wces, ? bm	II	48
Sphaeroceridae / 2						
<i>Copromyza equina</i> Fallén, 1820	97	•	1500	hno	IV-X	131
<i>Crumomyia rohaceki</i> Norrbom & Kim, 1985	117	•	2005	e	II	48
Drosophilidae / 1						
<i>Scaptomyza (Scaptomyza) flava</i> (Fallén, 1823)	111	◆	1150-1200	h	VIII	44
Diastatidae / 1						
<i>Diastata costata</i> Meigen, 1830	97	•	1400	e, ? h	V-X	26
Ephydriidae / 26						
<i>Psilopa nitidula</i> Fallén, 1813	10, 97, 102, 103, 158	•	400-1600	pat	IV-X	34
<i>Psilopa polita</i> (Macquart, 1835)	10, 55, 97, 158	◆◆	400-1600	dp	IV-X	34
<i>Hydrellia griseola</i> (Fallén, 1813)	8, 97, 102, 104, 124, 153, 158	•	850-2196	sk	IV-IX	35
<i>Hydrellia maura</i> Meigen, 1838	64, 102	•	1500-1600	wp	IV-X	35; 28,
<i>Dichaeta caudata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	14		400	h	V-X	35
<i>Notiphila (Notiphila) cinerea</i> Fallén, 1813	97	•	1400	tp, ? hop	V-X	35
<i>Notiphila (Notiphila) dorsata</i> Stenhammar, 1844	14		400	dp, ? wcp	V-X	35
<i>Notiphila graecula</i> Becker, 1926	97	•	1400	ewca	V-X	28, 35
<i>Notiphila nigricornis</i> Stenhammar, 1844	97	•	1400	wcp	V-IX	28, 35
<i>Dicrocerina obscurella</i> (Fallén, 1813)	14		400	hnat	IV-X	28, 37
<i>Nostima picta</i> (Fallén, 1813)	10, 84, 158	•	400-2400	hn	IV-X	28, 36
<i>Philygria stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)	8, 84, 97, 102, 153	•	1400-2400	e	IV-X	28, 36
<i>Hyadina guttata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	9	•	1400	tp	V-X	28, 36
<i>Parydra (Chaetopnacia) fossarum</i> (Haliday, 1833)	8	•	2000	h	IV-IX	28, 38
<i>Parydra (Parydra) coarctata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	64, 97	•	1500-1600	tp, ? hop	IV-X	28, 38
<i>Parydra (Parydra) cognata</i> Loew, 1860	14, 64, 97,	•	400-1600	wp	V-X	28, 38
<i>Parydra (Parydra) littoralis</i> (Meigen, 1830)	8, 10, 44, 97, 102, 158	◆◆	400-2000	wp	V-IX	28, 38

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Scatophila caviceps</i> (Stenhammar, 1844)	14		400	28, 38
<i>Linnellia quadrata</i> (Fallén, 1813)	84	●	2300	28, 38
<i>Lamproscatella bimaculata</i> Hendel, 1933	22	●	2000	28, 38
<i>Lamproscatella sibilans</i> (Haliday, 1833)	8	●	2000	28
<i>Lamproscatella unipunctata</i> (Becker, 1907)	8, 22, 84	●	2000	28, 38
<i>Scatella (Neoscatella) subguttata</i> (Meigen, 1830)	8, 97	●	2000	28, 38
<i>Scatella (Scatella) paludum</i> (Meigen, 1830)	8, 45, 97	◆	900-2000	28, 38
<i>Scatella (Scatella) stagnalis</i> (Fallén, 1813)	8, 97,	●	1400-2200	28, 38
<i>Scatella (Scatella) tenuicosta</i> Collin, 1930	8, 97	●	1400-2200	28, 38
CALYPTRATA				
Hippoboscidae / 1				
<i>Hippobosca equina</i> Linnaeus 1758	55, 122	◆	1350-2100	+++
<i>Hippobosca longipennis</i> Fabricius 1805	21		1200-1400	16
Scathophagidae / 2				
<i>Norellisoma armipes</i> (Meigen, 1826)	85	●	2500	145
<i>Scathophaga stercoraria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	23, 39, 97, 109, 111	●	550-2100	102, 131
Anthomyiidae / 3				
<i>Delia radicum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	39		550	45
<i>Egle parva</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	14, 97	●	400-1500	131
<i>Hylemya vagans</i> (Panzer, 1798)	97	●	1500	131
Fanniidae / 2				
<i>Fannia canicularis</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	39, 66, 111	◆	550-1960	125
<i>Fannia scalaris</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	39, 66, 111	◆	550-1960	125
Muscidae / 55				
<i>Muscina levida</i> (Harris, 1780)	39, 66, 111	◆	550-1960	125
<i>Muscina stabulans</i> (Fallén, 1817)	39, 66, 111	◆	550-1960	125
<i>Thricops cunctans</i> (Meigen, 1826)	109	●	1500-2000	130
<i>Thricops longipes</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	109	●	900-2000	130

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Thricops nigrifrons</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	109	•	600-1900	eswa	130, 145
<i>Thricops nigritellus</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	109	•	1200-2000	wes	130
<i>Drymeia fasciculata</i> (Stein, 1916)	66, 69	•	1500-2000	se, ? m	126, 130
<i>Hydrotaea ignava</i> (Harris, 1780)	14		400	ho	125
<i>Hydrotaea irritans</i> (Fallen, 1823)	97, 109	•	1500	tp	131
<i>Hydrotaea meteorica</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	97, 109	•	1500	h	130, 131
<i>Hydrotaea similis</i> Meade, 1887	158		1374	tp	127
<i>Hydrotaea tuberculata</i> Rondani, 1866	97, 109	•	1500	h	131
<i>Mesembrina intermedia</i> Zetterstedt, 1849	109	•	700-1700	wces	127, 130
<i>Mesembrina meridiana</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	tp	127
<i>Mesembrina resplendens</i> Wahlberg, 1844	21, 109,	•	900-1900	hoes	53, 57, 127, 130
<i>Poletes lardarius</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	109	•	400-2000	pat	125, 129
<i>Musca amita</i> Hennig, 1964	39, 66, 111	•♦	550-1960	hoes	125
<i>Musca autumnalis</i> De Geer, 1776	39, 66, 109, 111	•♦	550-2300	hpt	125, 129, 131
<i>Musca domestica</i> Linnaeus, 1758	14, 109, 111	♦	400-2200	k	102, 125, 129, 130
<i>Musca tempestiva</i> Fallén, 1817	109		400-1200	ppt	125
<i>Musca vitripennis</i> Meigen, 1826	39, 66, 111	•♦	550-1960	po	125
<i>Morella aenescens</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	109	•	600-1500	tp	130
<i>Morella podagrica</i> (Loew, 1857)	13, 21	•	590-1400	h	128
<i>Morella simplex</i> (Loew, 1857)	14, 21, 39, 110	•	400-1400	tp	125, 145, 169
<i>Neomyia cornicina</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	14, 21, 97	•	400-1500	sk	125, 131, 169
<i>Pyrellia vivida</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	39, 66, 109, 111	•♦	550-2000	po	125, 130
<i>Dasyphora gussakovskii</i> Zimin, 1947	118, 145, 146	•	1800-2000	po	125, 130
<i>Dasyphora penicillata</i> (Egger, 1865)	39, 66, 111	•♦	550-1960	wp	125
<i>Dasyphora pratorum</i> (Meigen, 1826)	39, 66, 97, 111	•♦	550-1960	wp	125, 131
<i>Haematobia irritans</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200	hn	60
<i>Phaonia angelicae</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	21, 109	•	500-1800	tp	127, 130
<i>Phaonia bitincta</i> (Rondani 1866)	97	•	1500	e	130, 131

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Phaonia errans</i> (Meigen, 1826)	21		1200-1400	h	145
<i>Phaonia lugubris</i> (Meigen, 1826)	21, 109	●	600-1800	h	127, 130
<i>Phaonia rufiventris</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	97	●	1500	? wp	131
<i>Phaonia scutellata</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	158		1374	ena	130
<i>Phaonia serva</i> (Meigen, 1826)	21, 109		1200-1400	h	125, 130
<i>Helina annosa</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	21, 109		1200-1400	h	126, 130
<i>Helina ciliatocosta</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	109	●	400-1500	e	130
<i>Helina depuncta</i> (Fallén, 1825)	97	●	1500	esca	131
<i>Helina evecta</i> (Harris, 1780)	109		400-2000	ppt, ? hpt	130
<i>Helina latitarsis</i> Ringdahl, 1924	21, 109		1200-1400	ean	127, 130
<i>Helina montana</i> (Rondani, 1866)	109, 158,		1374	dpo, ? wpo	127, 130
<i>Helina obscurata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	21, 109, 130, 137	●	1200-1900	h	127, 130
<i>Helina pubiseta</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	109, 158		1500	e	127, 130
<i>Helina reversio</i> (Harris, 1780)	21, 109		1200-1400	h, ? ho	127
<i>Mydaea corni</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	97	●	1500	hop	131
<i>Myospila mediatubunda</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	14		400	hno	125
<i>Hebecnema fumosa</i> (Meigen, 1826)	109	●	600-2000	po	130
<i>Hebecnema umbratica</i> (Meigen, 1826)	97	●	1500	ho	131
<i>Hebecnema vespertina</i> (Fallén, 1823)	109, 111	◆	1150-1500	h	125, 130
<i>Graphomya maculata</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	109, 111	◆	1150-1300	po, ? poa	125, 130
<i>Spilogona carbonella</i> (Zetterstedt, 1845)	109			ean	130
<i>Spilogona denigrata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	109, 158		1500	e	127, 130
<i>Spilogona dispar</i> (Fallén, 1823)	66, 97, 109	●	1500-2000	wes	126, 130, 231
Calliphoridae / 14					
<i>Bellardia pandia</i> (Walker 1849)	61	◆	1600	e	98, 99
<i>Calliphora genarum</i> (Zetterstedt 1838)	61	◆	1600	h	98, 99
<i>Calliphora vicina</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	100		900	k	+++
<i>Calliphora vomitoria</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	ha	62

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References	
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical		Fenology
<i>Lucilia caesar</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	14, 111	◆	400-1300	hop	IV-X	+++
<i>Lucilia richardsi</i> Collin, 1926	Slavovo		900-1100	e	VIII-IX	98
<i>Lucilia sericata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	21, 23, 39, 111, 135, 140	◆◆	550-2100	k	VI-X	98, 102, 169
<i>Lucilia silvarum</i> (Meigen, 1826)	109	●		hn	IV-X	102
<i>Protophormia terraeovae</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	97	●	1500	h	IV-XI	131
<i>Pollenia dasyopoda</i> Portschiński, 1881	135		900-1100	wpo	VIII-IX	100
<i>Pollenia rudis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	61, 111, 135	◆	900-1600	hpta	III-XI	98, 102
<i>Pollenia tenuiforceps</i> Séguin, 1928	21		1200-1400	ena	VI, VIII	169
<i>Pollenia viatica</i> Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830	61	◆	1600	ewca	VII	100
<i>Rhyncomyia cyanescens</i> (Loew, 1844)	135		900-1100	hom	VIII-X	98
Sarcophagidae / 24						
<i>Pterella grisea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	135		1200	wcp	VIII	98
<i>Taxigramma stictica</i> (Meigen, 1830)	135		1100	ena	VIII	98
<i>Metopia argyrocephala</i> (Meigen, 1824)	135		1100	hno	VIII-X	98
<i>Metopia campestris</i> (Fallén, 1810)	61, 135	◆	900-1600	h	VIII-IX	98
<i>Brachicoma devia</i> (Fallén, 1820)	21, 143	●	1200-1800	h	VII-VIII	61, 98
<i>Eurychaeta muscaria</i> (Meigen, 1826)	21, 61	◆	1200-1600	ena	VII-VIII	61, 98
<i>Blaesoxipha (Blaesoxipha) unguolata</i> (Pandellé, 1896)	61	◆	1600	ena	VIII	98
<i>Blaesoxipha (Servaisia) rossica</i> Villeneuve, 191	135		900-1200	esca	VIII-IX	98
<i>Ravinia pernix</i> (Harris, 1780)	109, 111, 135	◆	900-1200	po	V-X	98, 102
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) agrata</i> Rondani, 1860	111	◆	1150	e	IX	151
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) noverca</i> Rondani, 1860	61, 111	◆	1150-1600	e	VI-VIII	98, 151
<i>Sarcophaga (Helicophagella) rosellei</i> Böttcher, 1912	111	◆	1150	des	VII	151
<i>Sarcophaga (Krameromyia) anaces</i> Walker, 1849	138		630-700	h	VII	151
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteromychia) benaci</i> Böttcher, 1913	61, 135	◆	1600	cse	VIII-IX	98
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteromychia) dissimilis</i> Meigen, 1826	14, 21, 61	◆	400-1600	des	VI, VIII-IX	61, 98
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteromychia) infantilis</i> Böttcher, 1913	138		630-700	e	VII-VIII	151
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteromychia) porrecta</i> (Böttcher, 1913)	109	●	1200-2200	se, m	VI-VII	151

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteromychia) schineri</i> Bezzi, 1891	61, 111	◆	1150-1600	VII- VIII 98; 151
<i>Sarcophaga (Heteromychia) vagans</i> Meigen, 1826	61, 111, 135	◆	1150-1600	V-VIII 98, 145
<i>Sarcophaga (Bercaea) africa</i> (Wiedemann, 1824)	14		400	V-X 61, 98
<i>Sarcophaga (Liosarcophaga) jacobsoni</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	14		400	VIII-X 100
<i>Sarcophaga (Liosarcophaga) portschinskyi</i> (Rohdendorf, 1937)	1		1200-1800	VIII-IX 98
<i>Sarcophaga (Parasarcophaga) albiceps</i> Meigen, 182	14, 21		400-1400	VI-IX 36, 145
<i>Sarcophaga (Robineauella) caerulea</i> Zetterstedt, 1838	21, 61	◆	1200-1600	VII-IX 61, 98
Rhinophoridae / 1				
<i>Stevenia umbratica</i> (Fallén, 1820)	135		1000-1100	VIII 98, 99
Gasterophilidae / 3				
<i>Gasterophilus haemorrhoidalis</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21		1200-1400	
<i>Gasterophilus intestinalis</i> (De Geer, 1776)	21, 109		1200-1400	VII 55, 102
<i>Gasterophilus pecorum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21		1200-1400	VII-VIII 55
Tachinidae / 162				
<i>Exorista (Exorista) larvarum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	13, 14, 59, 96, 100, 103, 116, 129		360-1000	V-IX 87, +++
<i>Exorista (Adenia) mimula</i> (Meigen, 1824)	14, 29, 56, 129, 135		360-1200	V-VIII 98, +++
<i>Exorista (Adenia) rustica</i> (Fallén, 1810)	14, 21, 61, 88, 103, 135	◆◆	450-1600	VI-X 98, +++
<i>Chetogena acuminata</i> Rondani, 1859	14, 135,		450-1000	VII-IX 98
<i>Chetogena filipalpis</i> Rondani, 1859	14, 61, 135	◆	450-1600	V, VI-X 98
<i>Parasetigena silvestris</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863)	34		1400	V-VII +++
<i>Phorocera assimilis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	10, 14		400-450	IV-VII 145, 173
<i>Phorocera grandis</i> (Rondani, 1859)	11		440	IV-VI +++
<i>Phorocera obscura</i> (Fallén, 1810)	80, 106		900-1000	V-VII +++
<i>Meigenia dorsalis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	46, 61, 88, 111, 160	◆◆	600-1250	V-X 98, 99
<i>Meigenia majuscula</i> (Rondani, 1859)	14		400	IV-IX 98, 99
<i>Meigenia mutabilis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	23, 55, 61, 97, 100, 108, 112, 118, 119, 129, 136, 140, 146	◆◆	360-2350	IV-X 98, +++

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Steleoneura czernyi</i> Stein, 1924	14		400-500	mca	VII-VIII 99
<i>Medina luctuosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	115	◆	1000-1200	hoes	V-IX 98, 99
<i>Admontia podomyia</i> Brauer & Bergenstamm, 1889	118, 140	◆◆	1900-2200	e, bm	V-VIII +++
<i>Oswaldia spectabilis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	96, 103		850-1150	e	VI-VIII +++
<i>Eryniopsis antennata</i> (Rondani, 1861)	110, 129		360-545	? hom, h*	IV-IX +++
<i>Blondelia nigripes</i> (Fallén, 1810)	21, 55, 97, 108, 118, 127, 129, 135, 146, 159	◆◆	360-2360	tp, h*	V-X 98, +++
<i>Compsitura concinnata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	46, 55, 110, 116, 158	◆	500-1400	hoes, h*	IV-IX +++
<i>Smidtia amoena</i> (Meigen, 1824)	100, 110		500-900	hoes	V-VI +++
<i>Winthemia quadripustulata</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	21, 61, 111	◆◆	1150-1400	h	V-X 98, +++
<i>Aplomya confinis</i> (Fallén, 1820)	55, 61, 97, 111, 135	◆◆	400-1650	hop	V-IX 98, +++
<i>Epicampocera succincta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21, 46, 55, 104	◆◆	1200-1500	tp	V-IX +++
<i>Phryxe nemea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	46, 55, 61, 100, 111, 127, 140, 153	◆◆	800-1900	hoes	V-X 98, +++
<i>Phryxe vulgaris</i> (Fallén, 1810)	21, 55, 97, 103, 116, 127, 141, 158	◆◆	1000-2000	h	V-X +++
<i>Periarctiopsis scutellaris</i> (Fallén, 1820)	14, 135		500-1100	wces	V-VIII 98
<i>Pseudoperichaeta nigrolineata</i> (Walker, 1853)	55	◆	1500	des	V-VIII +++
<i>Drino atopivora</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	116, 128, 158	◆	900-1300	sp	V-VIII +++
<i>Drino inconspicua</i> (Meigen, 1830)	46, 100, 158		1000-1300	wces	V-X +++
<i>Drino vicina</i> (Zetterstedt, 1849)	135		900	wces	VI-VIII 98
<i>Huebneria affinis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	66, 96	●	900-2000	ess	IV-X +++
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) gnava</i> (Meigen, 1824)	13, 37, 116, 138		690-1000	des	V-VIII +++
<i>Carcelia (Carcelia) lucorum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	34		1400	tp	V-X +++
<i>Platymya fimbriata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	136, 146	●	2200-2370	tp, bm	V-IX +++
<i>Eumeca linearicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	13, 158		600-1350	hoes	V-IX +++
<i>Eumeca mitis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	115	◆	1300	hoes	V-IX, VIII 98
<i>Zenillia tibatrix</i> (Panzer, 1798)	61	◆	1300-1600	hoes	IV-VIII 98
<i>Clemelis pullata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	118, 135, 144	●	900-2350	wcp	V-IX 98, +++

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo- graphical	
<i>Pales pavida</i> (Meigen, 1824)	14, 116, 158		400-1350	hop	V-X 87, + + +
<i>Pales pumicata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	61	◆	1300-1600	nm	V-VIII 98
<i>Ceromasia rubrifrons</i> (Macquart, 1834)	115, 140	◆	800-1400	hoes	VII-IX 98, 99
<i>Allophorocera ferruginea</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21, 55, 96, 111, 140, 142, 145	◆◆	900-1950	hoes	V-IX 173, + + +
<i>Allophorocera pachystyla</i> (Macquart, 1850)	109	●	1800-2000	e, m	VII-VIII 86
<i>Eurysphaea scutellaris</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1848)	14, 100, 129		350-800	e	VI-VII + + +
<i>Sturmia bella</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21, 135		900-1400	po	V-IX 98, + + +
<i>Blepharipa pratensis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	16, 55, 59, 110, 111		500-1400	tp, h*	V-VII + + +
<i>Masicera pannoniae</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	14, 104		400-1000	wp	V-VII + + +
<i>Masicera silvatica</i> (Fallén, 1810)	135		900-1000	e	V-VIII 98, 99
<i>Prosopaea nigricans</i> (Egger, 1861)	36, 59, 79, 106, 135		800-1100	wcp	V-VIII 98, + + +
<i>Gonia bimaculata</i> Wiedemann, 1819	14, 110, 138, 156		400-1000	atm	III-IX 98, 99, + + +
<i>Gonia capitata</i> (De Geer, 1776)	21, 74, 97, 103, 111, 140, 158	◆◆	500-1900	wcp	V-VIII 145
<i>Spallanzania hebes</i> (Fallén, 1820)	10, 14, 36, 110		400-600	ho	V-IX 98, 99, + + +
<i>Tachina (Tachina) grossa</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	21, 75, 158		350-1300	hoes	V-VIII + + +
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) casta</i> (Rondani, 1859)	110		500-550	nm	IX-X + + +
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) fera</i> (Linnaeus, 1761)	4, 14, 21, 34, 61, 66, 73, 83, 97, 111, 126, 137, 144, 153	◆◆	340-1900	hop	V-X 98, 99, 145, + + +
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) magnicornis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	14, 22, 35, 41, 45, 53, 55, 66, 104, 109, 111, 127, 140, 144, 158, 160	◆◆	350-1900	hop	V-X 98, 99, 102, 170, + + +
<i>Tachina (Eudoromyia) nupta</i> (Rondani, 1859)	21, 24, 36, 37, 65, 110, 111, 129	◆◆	300-1750	tp	V-IX + + +
<i>Tachina (Servillia) lurida</i> (Fabricius, 1781)	16, 39, 110		350-660	wp	III-VI + + +
<i>Tachina (Echinogaster) praeceps</i> Meigen, 1824	14, 21, 37, 158		350-1300	wp	V-IX 98, + + +
<i>Nowickia (Nowickia) marklini</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	3, 21, 23, 108, 118, 136, 141, 144	◆◆	1200-2300	h, ? bm	VII-VIII 86, + + +
<i>Nowickia (Fabriciella) atripalpis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1863)	21, 38, 103, 108, 118, 120, 126, 140, 158	◆◆	1150-2250	hoes, bm	VII-IX 86, + + +

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Nowickia (Fabriciella) ferox</i> (Panzer, 1809)	22, 26, 55, 97, 144, 154	◆◆	900-2300	wes	145, + + +
<i>Nowickia (Fabriciella) rondanii</i> (Giglio-Tos, 1890)	6, 97, 138, 158	●	700-1600	sess	+ + +
<i>Peleteria rubescens</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	14, 55, 61, 104, 135, 141, 158	◆◆	400-2000	tp	98, 99, + + +
<i>Peleteria ruficornis</i> (Macquart, 1835)	14, 110		350-500	msws	98, + + +
<i>Peleteria varia</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	16, 96, 97	●	480-1450	ppta	+ + +
<i>Linnaemya (Linnaemya) comita</i> (Fallén, 1810)	103, 110, 111, 158, 160	◆	400-1300	ho	+ + +
<i>Linnaemya (Bonellinyya) impudica</i> (Rondani, 1859)	14, 16, 106, 129, 155		350-1300	cse	98, + + +
<i>Linnaemya (Ophina) haemorrhoidalis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	14, 41, 132, 140, 145, 153	◆◆	500-1900	hoes, bm	+ + +
<i>Linnaemya (Ophina) helvetica</i> Herting, 1963	16, 17		500-700	cse	+ + +
<i>Linnaemya (Ophina) perinealis</i> Pandellé, 1895	14		400	hoes	170
<i>Linnaemya (Ophina) picta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	39, 109, 111	◆	550-1250	po	102, + + +
<i>Linnaemya (Homoeonychia) frater</i> (Rondani, 1859)	14		400	hom	98
<i>Chrysosomopsis aurata</i> (Fallén, 1820)	135		900	hoes	98
<i>Ernestia puparum</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	111	◆	1200	hoes	102
<i>Ernestia rudis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	61, 88, 112	◆	900-1750	tp	+ + +
<i>Eurithia caesia</i> (Fallén, 1810)	96, 142		900-1700	hoes	+ + +
<i>Hyalurgus lucidus</i> (Meigen, 1824)	97, 112, 144, 154,	◆◆	1500-1800	wces, bm	+ + +
<i>Zophomyia temula</i> (Scopoli, 1763)	18, 39, 55, 68, 81, 111	◆◆	600-1750	tp	102, + + +
<i>Loewia brevifrons</i> (Rondani, 1856)	14, 104, 100		400-900	nm	+ + +
<i>Pseudopachystylum gonioides</i> (Zetterstedt, 1838)	21		1350	hoes	86
<i>Macquartia chalconota</i> (Meigen, 1824)	104, 158		900-1300	wes	+ + +
<i>Macquartia dispar</i> (Fallén, 1820)	21, 111, 112, 100	◆	600-1400	ess	+ + +
<i>Macquartia grisea</i> (Fallén, 1810)	160		600-700	e	+ + +
<i>Macquartia praefica</i> (Meigen, 1824)	13, 59, 104, 156,		600-1250	hom	+ + +
<i>Macquartia tenebricosa</i> (Meigen, 1824)	14, 21, 55, 61, 111, 144	◆	400-1600	wcp	98, 99, 170, + + +
<i>Macquartia tessellum</i> (Meigen, 1824)	61	◆	1300-1400	mca	98
<i>Phytomyia abnormis</i> (Stein, 1924)	61	◆	1000-1500	se	98, 99

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Graphogaster brunnescens</i> Villeneuve, 1907	14		400	170
<i>Actia crassicornis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	13, 59, 127	●	600-1500	+++
<i>Actia infantula</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	14, 135		400-1000	98
<i>Peribaea tibialis</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851)	110, 156		550-1000	+++
<i>Siphona cristata</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	16, 59, 111		480-1150	+++
<i>Aphria latifrons</i> Villeneuve, 1908	14, 135		900	98
<i>Aphria longirostris</i> (Meigen, 1824)	39, 66, 144	●	600-2000	+++
<i>Demoticus plebejus</i> (Fallén, 1810)	14, 135		900-1100	98
<i>Bithia glirina</i> (Rondani, 1861)	55, 129	◆	360-1450	+++
<i>Bithia modesta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	32, 83		460-1200	+++
<i>Leskia aurea</i> (Fallén, 1820)	33, 96, 110, 156		700-900	+++
<i>Mimitho rufiventris</i> (Fallén, 1817)	45, 129		350-900	+++
<i>Microphthalma europaea</i> Egger, 1860	110		500-600	+++
<i>Trixa caerulescens</i> Meigen, 1824	14		400	172
<i>Trixa conspersa</i> (Harris, 1776)	14		400	172
<i>Billaea fortis</i> (Rondani, 1862)	17		650-800	+++
<i>Billaea irrorata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	110, 139		330-550	+++
<i>Billaea pectinata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	14, 46		400-1200	98, +++
<i>Billaea triangulifera</i> (Zetterstedt, 1844)	46, 156		1000-1200	+++
<i>Dinera carinifrons</i> (Fallén, 1817)	21, 37, 55, 56, 60, 61, 66, 78, 153	◆◆	400-2550	98, 99, +++
<i>Dinera ferina</i> (Fallén, 1817)	14, 22, 97, 135	●	500-1600	98, +++
<i>Dinera grisescens</i> (Fallen, 1817)	14		400-500	98
<i>Estheria cristata</i> (Meigen, 1826)	158		1374	86
<i>Estheria petiolata</i> (Bonsdorff, 1866)	22, 106, 116, 158	●	1000-1600	+++
<i>Estheria picta</i> (Meigen, 1826)	14, 106, 109, 128, 158	●	400-1600	98, +++
<i>Dexia rustica</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	13, 104		600-1100	+++

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution				References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	Areo-graphical	
<i>Prosema siberita</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	14, 100, 135, 153	●	500-1600	hpta	98, +++
<i>Zeuxia brevicornis</i> (Egger, 1860)	14		400	nmca	172
<i>Zeuxia cinerea</i> Meigen, 1826	135, 141	◆◆	500-2000	wp	98, +++
<i>Zeuxia erythraea</i> (Egger, 1856)	14		400	nm	172
<i>Eriothrix apenninus</i> (Rondani, 1862)	8, 55, 118	◆◆	1350-2350	wp	+++
<i>Eriothrix rufomaculatus</i> (De Geer, 1776)	57, 66, 97, 111, 119, 124	◆◆	1150-2300	tp	+++
<i>Ramonda spathulata</i> (Fallén, 1820)	55	◆	1350-1475	tp	+++
<i>Periscepsia carbonaria</i> (Panzer, 1798)	13		600-700	ppt	+++
<i>Athrycia trepida</i> (Meigen, 1824)	13, 14, 100, 111	◆	400-1200	tp	+++
<i>Voria ruralis</i> (Fallén, 1810)	14, 21, 61, 112, 145, 153	◆	400-1800	k	98, +++
<i>Phyllomya volvulus</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	111	◆	1150-1200	hoes	98
<i>Theilaira nigripes</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	13, 14		400-670	tp	+++
<i>Halidayia aurea</i> Egger, 1856	156		900-1000	hoes	+++
<i>Stomina calindrata</i> (Rondani, 1862)	13, 116	◆	670-1100	mca	+++
<i>Stomina iners</i> (Meigen, 1838)	135		900-1000	hom	98
<i>Stomina tachinoides</i> (Fallén, 1817)	14		400	wcp	98
<i>Rhamphina pedemontana</i> (Meigen, 1824)	100, 158		800-1300	se, ? nm	+++
<i>Dufouria nigrita</i> (Fallén, 1810)	14, 13, 59		400-900	wcp	+++
<i>Eliozeta helluo</i> (Fabricius, 1805)	10, 14, 100		400-800	tp	+++
<i>Eliozeta pellucens</i> (Fallén, 1820)	10, 58, 59		400-900	des	+++
<i>Clytiomya continua</i> (Panzer, 1798)	33, 28, 129		360-1000	tp	+++
<i>Ectophasia crassipennis</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	10, 13, 14, 59, 76, 81, 100, 103, 111, 116	◆	350-1200	tp	98, +++
<i>Ectophasia oblonga</i> (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830)	10, 11, 80, 111, 138		300-1150	wp	+++
<i>Gymnosoma clavatum</i> (Rohdendorf, 1947)	41, 106, 144	●	500-1500	tp	+++
<i>Gymnosoma costatum</i> (Panzer, 1800)	100		800-1000	tp	+++
<i>Gymnosoma dolycoridis</i> Dupuis, 1961	46, 96, 135		500-1200	ess	+++

Table 3. Continued

Taxa	Distribution			References
	Localities of Rila	Parks	Vertical (m)	
<i>Gymnosoma inornatum</i> Zimin, 1966	10, 82, 111, 156		380-1150	V-IX +++
<i>Gymnosoma nitens</i> Meigen, 1824	28		1000	V-IX +++
<i>Gymnosoma rotundatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	14, 21, 45, 55, 103, 111, 126, 153, 156	◆◆	350-1600	V-IX 98, 102, 171, +++
<i>Elomya lateralis</i> (Meigen, 1824)	10, 37, 59, 106, 129		350-1400	V-VII +++
<i>Phasia (Phasia) aurulans</i> Meigen, 1824	14		400	V-IX 171
<i>Phasia (Phasia) hemiptera</i> (Fabricius, 1794)	14, 109		400	V-IX 145, 171
<i>Phasia (Phasia) obesa</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	14, 36, 55, 59, 97	◆◆	750-1500	V-X 171, +++
<i>Phasia (Phasia) subcoleoptera</i> (Linnaeus, 1767)	14, 36, 37, 103		400-1200	VI-X 171, +++
<i>Phasia (Hyalomya) pusilla</i> Meigen, 1824	14, 81, 104		350-1100	IV-X 171, +++
<i>Dionaea aurifrons</i> (Meigen, 1824)	11, 13		450-600	V-IX +++
<i>Leucostoma tetraptera</i> (Meigen, 1824)	14, 158		400-1300	VI-VIII 98, +++
<i>Clairvillia biguttata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	13, 135		500-700	V-VIII +++
<i>Labigastera forcipata</i> (Meigen, 1824)	59, 158		900-1300	VI-VIII +++
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) bicolor</i> (Olivier, 1812)	10, 13, 33, 37, 87, 100, 104, 111, 116, 129, 158	◆◆	400-1300	V-VIII +++
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) brassicaria</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	10, 14, 28, 46, 55, 97, 100, 109, 111, 126, 153, 158, 160	◆◆	350-1700	VI-IX 98, 102, +++
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) brevicornis</i> (Loew, 1844)	14, 96, 104, 116		450-1200	V-VIII 98, 99, +++
<i>Cylindromyia (Cylindromyia) pilipes</i> (Loew, 1844)	16, 59, 79		480-900	V-IX +++
<i>Cylindromyia (Ocypterula) pusilla</i> (Meigen, 1824)	21		1200-1300	V-VIII 145
<i>Cylindromyia (Dupuisia) crassa</i> (Loew, 1845)	59		900	V-VIII +++
<i>Cylindromyia (Calocyptera) intermedia</i> (Meigen, 1824)	14, 36, 103, 116, 158		400-1300	V-VIII 98, +++
<i>Besseria anthophila</i> (Loew, 1871)	113	◆	1300	VIII 98
<i>Phania funesta</i> (Meigen, 1824)	36, 58		450-1000	V-VIII +++

presented in the first two vegetation belts. Usually the scrutinised areographical complex is scantily presented and is not determinant for the zoogeographical characteristic of taxa of the Bulgarian terrestrial fauna. In a highly mobile forms (such as Diptera) the complex is better presented and can reach 20-25%. It is better presented in the Rila Mts. than the Pirin Mts. and includes 21.0% of Diptera. In the two-winged insects significant numbers of synanthropic and synbovil forms with cosmopolitan distribution occur. They have anthropogenic areas, structured with the development of human civilisation (before the beginning of contemporary research).

Species distributed only in the Palaeartic, but in more than one subregion (Palaeartic type).

Taxa, whose areas include more than one Palaeartic subregion in latitudinal direction, belong to this group. They are well represented in the high mobile groups and comprise about 25-30% of the species composition. A total of 259 species (25.8%) from this group, combined into 18 zoogeographical categories, has been established in the Rila Mts. (Table 4). Its character is determined by the Transpalaeartic (78 species – 7.8%), West Palaeartic (46 species – 4.6%) and European-North African (35 species – 3.5%) species which are the most numerous. The correlation of these categories remains the same in the separate vegetation belts of the Rila Mts. with small deviations, and ranges from 1.6% to 12.2% (one to 61 species). The Holopalaeartic, West and Central Palaeartic and Eurosiberian-Central Asian species are well presented (18-23 species or 1.8-2.3%). Eight species have a longitudinal disjunction of the areas with regard to Siberia and Central Asia (Tables 3 and 4). Probably some of these species are presented with sparse populations and will be studied in more detail as a result of further studies. Most often a latitudinal disjunction of the areas of this group lacks (GORODKOV, 1984; JOSIFOV, 1988; HUBENOV, 2015a). A significant portion of the species with wide vertical distribution (about 25%) - to this group. It includes from 11.5% to 31.2% (three to 196 species) of the species composition in the separate vegetation belts (Table 4). The vast areas and wide vertical distribution of the taxa of this group are an indication of the greater ecological flexibility of its species. This group is represented a little better in terms of relative abundance in the Pirin Mts. where it comprises 27.5% of the dipterans.

Species distributed within one subregion of the Palaeartic. This group (486 species – 48.5%) includes species with Eurosiberian (429 species – 42.8%) and Mediterranean (45 species – 4.5%) type

of distribution (Tables 3 and 4). Endemics are included in this group as well. The Mediterranean-Central Asian species are also included here according to KRYZHANOVSKY (1965) and LOPATIN (1989) who combine the Mediterranean and Central Asian subregions. The species with Mediterranean type of distribution are accepted in a general way and include Submediterranean, Subiranian and Pontian faunistic elements that could be considered separately as well (GRUEV & KUSMANOV 1994, 1999; GRUEV 1995, 2000d).

The Eurosiberian species include 13 areographical categories, of which the European (183 species – 18.2%), Holoeurosiberian (82 species – 8.2%), West Eurosiberian (42 species – 4.2%) and Disjunct Eurosiberian (34 species – 3.4%) taxa are best represented. The ratio of these categories is different for the separate families (the Holoeurosiberian, Disjunct Eurosiberian and European species of the family Tachinidae are almost equal in number as the Eurosiberian forms are 50% in total, while in other families the Central and South European species are better represented). The number of taxa of these categories found in the separate vegetation belts varies from 1.0% to 18.7% (one-138 species) and increases (as a percentage) with height up to 2200 m a.s.l. Most Eurosiberian species (as a percentage) are found in the beech and coniferous forest belts and the alpine zone as well. In the subalpine and alpine belts the Eurosiberian species predominate over the other zoogeographical categories (40.4-44.2%). A number of disjunctive areas are presented: a longitudinal disjunction for parts of Siberia and Central Asia (Tables 3 and 4) and a latitudinal disjunction with typical for the Eurosiberian complex boreomontane, boreoalpine and arctic-alpine distribution (GORODKOV, 1984; JOSIFOV, 1988; HUBENOV, 2015a). Of interest is the significant presence of Eurosiberian species in the first two vegetation belts of the Rila Mts., which can be explained in two ways: 1) It is possible that a part of these species to have unclear Palaeartic distribution; 2) It is supposed that the humid mountain valleys characterised with cooler climate, have facilitated the migration of the above-mentioned forms to the lowlands. Finding of Eurosiberian boreomontane forms at low altitudes has also been reported for other insect groups as Heteroptera, Cerambycidae (Coleoptera) and Tachinidae (Diptera) by JOSIFOV (1963, 1976), GEORGIEV & HUBENOV (2006), and HUBENOV (1992, 2008b). For Cerambycide this fact is due to the large deforestations of conifers in the first two vegetation belts. Probably because of

Table 4. Zoogeographical characteristics of Diptera (Insecta) according to the vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.

Areogeographical categories	Vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.							Pirin Mts. Total number, %
	Total number, %	Xerothermic oak forests – up to 500-700 m a.s.l.	Mesophyllitic and hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m a.s.l.	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.	Coniferous forests – from 1500-1600 m to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.	Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 m to 2500 m a.s.l.	Alpine vegetation – over 2400-2500 m a.s.l.	
Species distributed in Palearctic and out of it	258 (25.7)	79 (30.9)	92 (26.2)	196 (26.6)	74 (26.7)	31 (31.3)	11 (42.3)	156 (21.0)
NORTH TYPE	255 (25.4)	76 (29.7)	90 (25.6)	196 (26.6)	74 (26.7)	31 (31.3)	11 (42.3)	151 (20.3)
Cosmopolitan (k)	7 (0.7)	6 (2.3)	7 (2.0)	6 (0.8)	5 (1.8)			6 (0.8)
Semicosmopolitan (sk)	3 (0.3)	2 (0.8)	2 (0.6)	2 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)		3 (0.4)
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Neotropical (hptn)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)	1 (0.1)	2 (0.7)			1 (0.1)
Holarctic-Paleotropical-Australian (hpta)	5 (0.5)	2 (0.8)	3 (0.8)	4 (0.5)	2 (0.7)			3 (0.4)
Holarctic-Paleotropical (hpt)	2 (0.2)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)		1 (0.1)
Holarctic-Neotropical-Oriental (hno)	9 (0.9)	4 (1.6)	3 (0.8)	6 (0.8)	1 (0.4)	2 (2.0)	1 (3.8)	5 (0.7)
Holarctic-Neotropical-Afrotropical (hnat)	2 (0.2)	2 (0.8)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)			2 (0.3)
Holarctic-Oriental-Australian (hoa)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)				
Holarctic-Afrotropical-Australian (hata)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)				
Holarctic-Neotropical (hn)	4 (0.4)	2 (0.8)	3 (0.8)	2 (0.3)	2 (0.7)	2 (2.0)	1 (3.8)	3 (0.4)
Holarctic-Afrotropical (hat)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	3 (0.3)	2 (0.7)			1 (0.1)
Holarctic-Oriental (ho)	31 (3.1)	10 (3.9)	12 (3.4)	23 (3.1)	9 (3.2)	1 (1.0)	1 (3.8)	23 (3.1)
Holarctic-Australian (ha)	5 (0.5)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)	3 (0.3)				2 (0.3)
Palearctic-Paleotropical-Australian (ppta)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)			4 (0.5)
Palearctic-Afrotropical-Australian (pata)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)				
Palearctic-Oriental-Australian (poa)	2 (0.2)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.3)				
Palearctic-Paleotropical (ppt)	6 (0.6)	3 (1.2)	3 (0.8)	5 (0.7)	1 (0.4)			4 (0.5)
Palearctic-Afrotropical (pat)	2 (0.2)	2 (0.8)	2 (0.6)	2 (0.3)	1 (0.4)			3 (0.4)
Palearctic-Oriental (po)	29 (2.9)	11 (4.3)	12 (3.4)	26 (3.5)	9 (3.2)	3 (3.0)	2 (7.7)	13 (1.7)
Palearctic-Australian (pa)	1 (0.1)				1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)	1 (3.8)	1 (0.1)
West Palearctic-Oriental (wpo)	10 (1.0)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)	7 (0.9)	1 (0.4)			2 (0.3)
Disjunct Palearctic-Oriental (dpo)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)				1 (0.1)

Table 3. Continued

Areographical categories	Vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.							Pirin Mts. Total numbers %
	Total numbers %	Xerothermic oak forests – up to 500-700 m a.s.l.	Mesophyllitic and hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m a.s.l.	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.	Coniferous forests – from 1500-1600 m to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.	Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 m to 2500 m a.s.l.	Alpine vegetation – over 2400-2500 m a.s.l.	
West Palaearctic-Afrotropical (wpat)	124 (12.4)	25 (9.8)	31 (8.8)	94 (12.8)	34 (12.3)	20 (20.2)	5 (19.2)	1 (0.1)
Holarctic (h)								72 (9.7)
SOUTH TYPE	3 (0.3)	3 (1.2)	2 (0.6)					5 (0.7)
South Palaearctic-Paleotropical-Australian (sppta)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)					1 (0.1)
South Palaearctic-Afrotropical (spat)								1 (0.1)
Paleotropical-Mediterranean (ptm)								1 (0.1)
Afrotropical-Mediterranean (atm)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)					1 (0.1)
Oriental-Mediterranean (om)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)						1 (0.1)
Species with Palaearctic distribution	745 (74.3)	177 (69.1)	259 (73.8)	540 (73.4)	203 (73.3)	68 (68.7)	15 (57.7)	586 (79.0)
PALAEARCTIC TYPE	259 (25.8)	80 (31.2)	103 (29.3)	196 (26.6)	75 (27.1)	24 (24.2)	3 (11.5)	204 (27.5)
Holopalaearctic (hop)	18 (1.8)	10 (3.9)	13 (3.7)	17 (2.3)	7 (2.5)			19 (2.6)
Transpalaearctic (tp)	78 (7.8)	30 (11.7)	43 (12.2)	61 (8.3)	21 (7.6)	8 (8.1)	1 (3.8)	58 (7.8)
West and Central Palaearctic (wcp)	23 (2.3)	11 (4.3)	11 (3.1)	18 (2.4)	6 (2.2)	2 (2.0)	1 (3.8)	24 (3.2)
West Palaearctic (wp)	46 (4.6)	14 (5.5)	14 (4.0)	35 (4.7)	16 (5.8)	6 (6.1)		26 (3.5)
Disjunct Palaearctic (dp)	8 (0.8)	4 (1.6)	2 (0.6)	4 (0.5)	1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)	1 (3.8)	13 (1.7)
South Palaearctic (sp)	3 (0.3)		1 (0.3)	3 (0.3)				2 (0.3)
European-Anatolian-North African (eanna)	1 (0.1)							
European-North African (ena)	35 (3.5)	4 (1.6)	8 (2.3)	27 (3.7)	12 (4.3)	3 (3.0)		26 (3.5)
Euroiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian (esanca)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)				
Euroiberian-Central Asian (esca)	22 (2.2)	3 (1.2)	5 (1.4)	13 (1.8)	5 (1.8)	1 (1.0)		8 (1.1)
West Euroiberian-Anatolian-Central Asian (wesanca)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)						
West Euroiberian-Central Asian (wesca)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)			2 (0.3)
West Euroiberian-Iran-Turanian (westit)	1 (0.1)				1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)		

Table 3. Continued

Areographical categories	Vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.							Pirin Mts. Total number, %
	Total number, %	Xerothermic oak forests – up to 500-700 m a.s.l.	Mesophyllitic and hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m a.s.l.	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.	Coniferous forests – from 1500-1600 m to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.	Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 m to 2500 m a.s.l.	Alpine vegetation – over 2400-2500 m a.s.l.	
European-Central Asian (eca)	2 (0.2)			1 (0.1)				3 (0.4)
East European-Central Asian (eeca)								1 (0.1)
European-West Central Asian (ewca)	4 (0.4)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	4 (0.5)	1 (0.4)			5 (0.7)
European-South-West Asian (eswa)	4 (0.4)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.3)	3 (1.1)			6 (0.8)
European-Iran-Turanian (eit)	8 (0.8)		3 (0.8)	7 (0.9)	1 (0.4)			8 (1.1)
European-Turanian (et)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.3)				3 (0.4)
EUROSIERIAN TYPE	429 (42.8)	78 (30.5)	139 (39.6)	315 (42.8)	119 (43.0)	40 (40.4)	11 (42.3)	328 (44.2)
Holoeurosiberian (hoes)	82 (8.2)	16 (6.2)	27 (7.7)	60 (8.1)	24 (8.7)	6 (6.1)	2 (7.7)	50 (6.7)
West and Central Eurosiberian (wces)	27 (2.7)	5 (1.9)	10 (2.8)	21 (2.8)	7 (2.5)	1 (1.0)	1 (3.8)	29 (3.9)
West Eurosiberian (wes)	42 (4.2)	8 (3.1)	14 (4.0)	31 (4.2)	8 (2.9)	2 (2.0)		27 (3.6)
Disjunct Eurosiberian (des)	34 (3.4)	7 (2.7)	14 (4.0)	22 (3.0)	11 (4.0)	1 (1.0)		39 (5.2)
European and South Siberian (ess)	6 (0.6)	4 (1.6)	4 (1.1)	5 (0.7)	1 (0.4)			11 (1.5)
European-Anatolian (ean)	10 (1.0)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)	5 (0.7)	3 (1.1)	2 (2.0)		4 (0.5)
European (e)	183 (18.2)	32 (12.5)	60 (17.1)	138 (18.7)	47 (17.0)	18 (18.2)	4 (15.4)	141 (19.0)
Central and East European (cee)	2 (0.2)			2 (0.3)				
Central and South European-Anatolian (csean)	5 (0.5)		1 (0.3)	5 (0.7)	4 (1.4)	2 (2.0)	2 (7.7)	3 (0.4)
Central and South-East European-Anatolian (cseean)	2 (0.2)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)		
Central and South-East European-Lebanonian (cseel)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)	1 (3.8)	
Central and South European (cse)	25 (2.5)	2 (0.8)	4 (1.1)	18 (2.4)	9 (3.2)	4 (4.0)	1 (3.8)	18 (2.4)
Central and South-East European (csee)	10 (1.0)	2 (0.8)	2 (0.6)	6 (0.8)	3 (1.1)	2 (2.0)		6 (0.8)
MEDITERRANEAN TYPE	45 (4.5)	19 (7.4)	17 (4.8)	23 (3.1)	6 (2.2)	2 (2.0)		41 (5.5)
Mediterranean and South Siberian (mss)	3 (0.3)			1 (0.1)				1 (0.1)
Mediterranean and South-West Siberian (mssws)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)					1 (0.1)

Table 3. Continued

Areographical categories	Vegetation belts of the Rila Mts.							Pirin Mts. Total number, %
	Total number, %	Xerothermic oak forests – up to 500-700 m a.s.l.	Mesophyllitic and xeromesophyllitic oak-hornbeam forests – from 600-700 m to 900-1000 m a.s.l.	Beech forests - from 900-1000 to 1500-1600 m a.s.l.	Coniferous forests – from 1500-1600 m to 2000-2200 m a.s.l.	Subalpine vegetation – from 2000-2200 m to 2500 m a.s.l.	Alpine vegetation – over 2400-2500 m a.s.l.	
Mediterranean-Central Asian (mca)	6 (0.6)	4 (1.6)	3 (0.8)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)		6 (0.8)	
North Mediterranean-Central Asian (nmca)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)						
Mediterranean-West Central Asian (mwca)	2 (0.2)	1 (0.4)		1 (0.1)			2 (0.3)	
Northeast Mediterranean-Iran-Turanian (nemit)							1 (0.1)	
Mediterranean-Turanian (mt)	1 (0.1)						2 (0.3)	
North Mediterranean-Turanian (nmt)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.1)			3 (0.4)	
South European and South Siberian (sess)	1 (0.1)		1 (0.3)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)		2 (0.3)	
Central and South European-Iran-Turanian (cseit)	2 (0.2)			1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)	
Central and South-East European-Iran-Turanian (cseet)							1 (0.1)	
Central and South European-North African (csena)	1 (0.1)		1 (0.3)	1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)		1 (0.1)	
South European-North African (sena)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)				
Holomediterranean (hom)	8 (0.8)	4 (1.6)	5 (1.4)	3 (0.3)			10 (1.3)	
North Mediterranean (nm)	6 (0.6)	4 (1.6)	1 (0.3)	2 (0.3)			4 (0.5)	
South European (se)	7 (0.7)	2 (0.8)	1 (0.3)	5 (0.7)	2 (0.7)	1 (1.0)	3 (0.4)	
South-East European (see)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)	1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)		
East Mediterranean (em)							1 (0.1)	
Balkan-Anatolian (ban)	3 (0.3)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.6)	2 (0.3)			2 (0.3)	
ENDEMICS	12 (1.2)			6 (0.8)	3 (1.1)	2 (2.0)	13 (1.7)	
Balkan subendemic (Ebs)	2 (0.2)				1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)	1 (0.1)	
Balkan endemic (Eb)	1 (0.1)			1 (0.1)			4 (0.5)	
Bulgarian endemic (Ebg)	7 (0.7)			5 (0.7)	1 (0.4)		6 (0.8)	
Regional endemic (Er)	2 (0.2)				1 (0.4)	1 (1.0)	2 (0.3)	
Total	1003	256 (25.5)	351 (35.0)	736 (73.4)	277 (27.6)	99 (9.9)	742	

this reason, many boreomontane and montane species that feed on conifers go down below 1000 m a.s.l. There are no significant differences between the Rila and Pirin Mountains with respect to the Eurosiberian species. This group includes 44.2% of the species composition of the Pirin Mts.

The Mediterranean species, combined into 16 zoogeographical categories, are presented mainly in the first three vegetation belts and their number rapidly decreases with altitude. Because of the big variety of these areas, this group is divided into many subgroups with different origin, distribution and ecological peculiarities of the taxa. This complexity contributes to establishing of various zoogeographical classifications for Bulgaria (JOSIFOV, 1981, 1986, 1988, 1999; GRUEV 1988, 1995, 2000a, 2000b, 2000c, 2000d, 2002; HEISS & JOSIFOV, 1990, GRUEV & KUSMANOV 1994, HUBENOV 1996, 2008a; POPOV, 2002). The Mediterranean species, established in one or two vegetation belts, prevail (Table 3). A significant percentage of these species and their relatively scarce populations are due to the lower ecological flexibility of the Mediterranean forms in comparison with the previous ones. The Mediterranean species include from 2.0 to 7.4% (two to 23 species) of Diptera of the separate vegetation belts in the Rila Mts. (Table 4). The Holomediterranean (eight species – 0.8%) and South European (seven species – 0.7%) species are the most numerous. In the subalpine belt two Mediterranean species are established (*Prosimulium petrosum* Rubtsov – South-East European species of the family Simuliidae and *Sarcophaga porrecta* Böttcher – South European species of the family Sarcophagidae). This could be Montane Mediterranean forms or species with unclear distribution. Mediterranean species have not been found in the alpine belt. When comparing with the Pirin Mts., there is a slightly higher percentage (5.5%) of the Mediterranean taxa which is related to the specific natural conditions and geographical location of this mountain. There are no significant differences in the distribution of the separate areogeographical categories in the Mediterranean species of the two mountains.

Endemics. This category includes taxa, which are not distributed outside the Balkan Peninsula. The percentage of endemism is low in Diptera (12 species – 1.2%). The Bulgarian endemic forms prevail. Endemic forms have not been established in the first two vegetation belts of the Rila Mts., in contrast to the Pirin Mts. The main part of the Rila endemic species is related to the beech, coniferous and subalpine belts (two-six species or 0.8-2.0%). This suggests that

these endemic species are postglacial neoendemics which are to be connected with the Eurosiberian forms. Local endemics have not been established among Diptera of the Rila Mts. The dipterans are rare and are mostly newly described taxa (one species in 1930, one – in 1940 and all the others after 1970). Of interest is the finding and describing of *Cremifania bulgarica* Papp, 2010 (family Cremifaniidae, reported from 2250 m a.s.l. – the third Palaearctic species of the family).

Conclusions

A total of 1003 two-winged species that belong to 58 families have been reported from the Rila Mts. The dipterous fauna can be divided into two main groups: 1) species with Mediterranean type of distribution (48 species or 4.8%): more thermophilic and distributed mainly in the southern parts of the Palaearctic. Three species of the southern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group, as well; 2) species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (955 species or 95.2%): more cold-resistant and widely distributed in the Palaearctic. Two hundred fifty-five species of northern type, distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it, can be formally related to this group as well. The zoogeographical character of the Tachinidae fauna is determined by the second group. The share of the two groups is different in the separate vegetation belts (Table 4).

Xerothermic oak forests (256 species or 25.5%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (22 species or 8.6%) the Mediterranean-Central Asian, Holomediterranean and North Mediterranean species are most numerous, and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (234 species or 91.4%) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic and European species are best represented. Endemic forms have not been established yet.

Mesophyllic and xeromesophyllic mixed forests (351 species or 35.0%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (19 species or 5.4%) the Mediterranean-Central Asian and Holomediterranean species prevail, and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (332 species – 94.6%) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, Holoeurosiberian and European species are best represented. The number of the Holarctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, European-North African, Holoeurosiberian, West and Central Eurosiberian, West Eurosiberian, Disjunct Eurosiberian, and European species is increased. The

percentage of the Mediterranean species decreases. Endemic forms have not been reported yet.

Beech forests (736 species or 73.4%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (23 species or 3.1%) the Mediterranean-Central Asian, Holomediterranean, and South European species are most numerous, and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (713 species – 96.9%) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, Holoeurosiberian, and European species are best represented. The species of southern type distributed in the Palaearctic and beyond it are not presented. The number of the Holarctic-Oriental, Palaearctic-Oriental, Holarctic, Transpalaearctic, West Palaearctic, European-North African, Holoeurosiberian, West and Central Eurosiberian, West Eurosiberian, and European species is increased. Endemic forms have been found. The Bulgarian endemics prevail. The percentage of the Mediterranean forms decreases.

Coniferous forests (277 species or 27.6%). From the species with Mediterranean type of distribution (six species or 2.2%) the South European species are most numerous, and from the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (271 species or 97.8%) the Holarctic, Transpalaearctic,

Holoeurosiberian and European species prevail. Of the areographical categories, 28 are not presented. The Cosmopolitan, Holarctic-Oriental, Palaearctic-Oriental, West Palaearctic, European-North African, and Disjunct Eurosiberian species are better represented. The number of the endemics and Mediterranean forms decreases.

Subalpine vegetation (99 species or 9.9%). Two species with Mediterranean type of distribution (South European and South-East European species) have been established. From the species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution (31 areographical categories) the Holarctic and European species are most numerous. This part of the Rila Mts. is poorly explored and with the exception of some families, the studies are fragmentary.

Alpine vegetation (26 species or 2.6%). Only species with Palaearctic and Eurosiberian type of distribution, belonging to 16 areographical categories, have been established. The Holarctic (five species) and European (four species) taxa are most numerous. The remaining categories are presented with one-two species each. One Bulgarian endemic (*Molophilus lautereri* Stary of the family Limoniidae) is recorded. Studies of this part of the Rila Mts. are almost lacking.

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The authors' address:

Zdravko Hubenov, National Museum of Natural History, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd. 1, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, e-mail: zhubenov@nmnhs.com

Двукрилите насекоми (Insecta: Diptera) на Рила

Здравко ХУБЕНОВ

(Резюме)

На Рила са установени 1003 вида двукрили, които спадат към 58 семейства. Най-многобройни са Tachinidae (162 вида – 16.1%) и Syrphidae (149 вида – 14.8%). Най-много видове са намерени в пояса на буковите гори (736 вида – 73.4%). Установените видове принадлежат към 84 ареалграфски категории. В зоогеографско отношение се очертават 2 основни групи: 1) видове с медитерански тип на разпространение (48 вида – 4.8%) – по-топлолюбиви и разпространени предимно в южните части на Палеарктика, към които формално са прибавени и 3 вида от южен тип, разпространени и извън Палеарктика; 2) видове с палеарктичен и евросибирски тип на разпространение (955 вида – 95.2%) – по-студенолюбиви и по-широко разпространени в Палеарктика, към които са отнесени и 255 вида от северен тип, разпространени и извън Палеарктика. От първата група най-много са холомедитеранските (8 вида – 0.8%) и южноевропейските (7 вида – 0.7%) форми. От втората група преобладават европейски (183 вида – 18.2%), холарктични (124 вида – 12.4%), холоевросибирски (82 вида – 8.2%) и транспалеарктични (78 вида – 7.8%) таксони. Ендемичните видове са 12 (1.2%). Зоогеографският характер на фауната се определя от втората група. Представено е разпределението на отделните категории в растителните пояси на Рила.